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The genomic basis of pathogenicity in
Fusarium solani species complex
infecting sea turtle

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Abstract

Fungi from the genus *Fusarium* is a common pathogen which infects plants, human, and animals. In particular, some members from the *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) which infect plants were well-studied because the most impacted hosts were agriculturally important. In animals, fusariosis caused by FSSC were increasingly reported from domestic, captive and wild animals in the recent decades. Whilst it is commonly reported as an opportunistic pathogen towards animals, most reports were only able to identify the disease causative FSSC members and describe its pathologic changes on the infected host. Sea turtle egg fusariosis (STEF) has been reported from around the globe and has caused huge mortality on this endangered animal. However, little is known regarding the ecology and pathology of STEF. Hence, this dissertation consists aims as follows: (1) determine the microbial diversity of nest sand which used to incubate sea turtle eggs, (2) determine the genomic basis of pathogenicity in FSSC isolates from dead sea turtle eggs and various host types, and (3) understand the pathology and infectious mechanism of FSSC on animal host. The outcome of this project should allow gain in fundamental knowledge regarding disease mechanism behind FSSC on animals, in order to suggest suitable conservation measures and practices to limit the infection.

Keywords: *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC), Sea turtle egg fusariosis (STEF), fusariosis, pathogenomics, host-pathogen interaction

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Chapter 1: General introduction

1.1 Emerging fungal diseases in wildlife

The filamentous ascomycete fungi *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) are commonly found in the environment of various substrate types (Zhang *et al.*, 2006) and has a notable image as a pathogen. This species complex comprised of about 60 species, and some of them are able to infect plants, animals, and human (Zhang *et al.*, 2006; Jain *et al.*, 2011; Fernando *et al.*, 2015; Vega-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2019). As a multi-kingdom pathogen, FSSC species and its associated infections (fusariosis) since then received much attentions due to its high virulence. Members of the FSSC were known as one of the most significant plant pathogens in the agriculture. Infected plants include common crops, legumes, cucurbits, trees, and ornamental flowering plant (Nemec, 1987; Li *et al.*, 2000; Boughalleb *et al.*, 2005; Romberg & Davis, 2007; Chung *et al.*, 2011; Porter *et al.*, 2015). Isolates can mostly be recovered from diseased stem and root of plants (Leslie & Summerell, 2006), which exhibited symptoms such as wilt, rot and lesion. Due to its ability which had caused huge loss in agricultural economy, studies were carried out in hope to understand and find solution to limit the infection.

Whilst abundant research was carried out regarding FSSC infection on plants, infection on animal host is less clear. Studies on human and animal hosts infected by FSSC had so far restricted only to reports, where most reports were only able to identify the disease causative FSSC members and describe its pathologic changes on the infected hosts. These incidences had recently increased in the recent decades, and it is now recognized as one of the most clinically and veterinary relevant species and emerging infectious disease due to its virulence. FSSC-related fusariosis has been reported on almost all class types in the animal kingdom, which includes the mammals, fishes, birds, reptiles, amphibians, and the invertebrates (Hurst, 2019). Fusariosis on humans were mostly cases involving *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* (Al-Hatmi *et al.*, 2016), which are members under the FSSC (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2008).

For instance, *F. keratoplasticum* had caused keratitis outbreak due to contamination of contact lens solution during 2005 in the U.S. (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2007; Short *et al.*, 2013). On the other hand, *F. solani* was the most frequently reported species in animals. Animals under fusariosis usually exhibited symptoms such as the keratitis and dermatitis, which can be superficial and disseminated within the body. *F. solani* had been identified from kidney lesions in dog (Kano *et al.*, 2002) and keratitis in horse (Hurst, 2019). Aquatic animals seem to be a more susceptible group by FSSC infection based on numerous reports. For instance, FSSC had been isolated from sharks, stingray, sea lion, sea horse, and crayfish (Crow *et al.*, 1995; Fernando *et al.*, 2015; Reisfeld *et al.*, 2019; Salter *et al.*, 2012; Salighehzadeh *et al.*, 2019). Most of the cases were fatal for the animals.

1.2 Fungal infection on sea turtle eggs

Another aquatic animal – the sea turtle, was recorded having lesion on wound caused by FSSC species (Cabañes *et al.*, 1997). In addition, nests of sea turtle eggs which incubate on the beach are also facing the risk of FSSC infection (Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014), which is now termed as sea turtle egg fusariosis (STEF; Smyth *et al.*, 2019). In particular, by two of the FSSC members – *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2008). Few of the first detail studies regarding fungal pathogen on unhatched sea turtle eggs were reported in Australia, initially identified as *F. solani* based on morphology (Phillott *et al.*, 2001; Phillott and Parmenter, 2001; Phillott, 2002; Phillott *et al.*, 2004). Using molecular methods, it is now understood that this fungal pathogen can be distinguished into two species as mentioned above. During the initial stage of infection, sea turtle eggs under fusariosis show signs of abnormal colours such as pink-reddish, purple, yellow, and blue spots on the inner and outer eggshell surface and turn blackish covering almost the whole egg during advance stage of infection (Figure 1; Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014). Koch postulates were fulfilled from infection assay using *F. keratoplasticum* on loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*) eggs (Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2010). This emerging fungal disease is now considered worldwide as FSSC were isolated from unhatched sea turtle eggs with STEF symptoms from most continents in recent years

(Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014; Rosado-Rodríguez and Maldonado-Ramírez, 2016; Siti Nordahliawate *et al.*, 2017). Yet, little is known about the environment between the co-existence of FSSC and animal host; and how this contribute to disease occurrence.

Hence, this project was designed with aims as follows:

1. To determine the microbial diversity of nest sand used to incubate sea turtle eggs;
2. To determine the genomic basis of pathogenicity in FSSC isolates from sea turtle eggs and various host types;
3. To understand the pathology and infectious mechanism of FSSC on animal host

Figure 1: Morphological symptoms of STEF on unhatched eggs. (A-C) Abnormal coloration showing pink to reddish, purple, yellow and blue spots on eggshell, yolk and dead embryo. (D-E) Advanced sign of infection showing blackish mat covering almost whole egg. (E) Whole clutch of nest with low hatching success exhibited serious sign of infection. (F) Symptomless unhatched egg.

Chapter 2: Microbial diversity and pathogen abundance in sea turtle hatcheries

2.1 Introduction

The establishment of hatchery has led to conservation success of endangered sea turtles. However, one of the unforeseen anthropogenic-induced impacts is the pathogen contamination of incubating-eggs in sea turtle hatchery. Fungal pathogens were observed on sea turtle eggs which were relocated to incubate in hatcheries (Siti Nordahliawate et al., 2017) or exposed to hatchery used-sand or eggshell decay (Patino-Martinez et al., 2011). Based on literatures, most infections were reported at natural nesting beaches (Phillott et al., 2004; Sarmiento-Ramírez et al., 2014) and few reported in hatcheries (Patino-Martinez et al., 2012; Siti Nordahliawate et al., 2017). Yet, little is known regarding disease occurrence on eggs in sea turtle hatchery in comparison with natural nesting beach, and to what extent that these pathogens, which occur ubiquitous in nature as well as the incubation environment, is affecting the incubating eggs.

Previous studies on microbial community in sea turtle nesting beach focused on arribada event, which is the mass nesting activity of Olive Ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) at Costa Rica (Honarvar et al., 2011; Bézy et al., 2015). These studies primarily aimed to determine the association between microbial abundance or richness and hatching success. Since sand-borne origin of FSSC infection on eggs was suspected (Patino-Martinez et al., 2011) and eggs of artificial incubation using sand from nesting beach exhibited symptoms of fungal colonization (Phillott and Parmenter, 2001), there is a need to encompass the relative abundances of pathogens for the analysis of microbial community structure in the environment for egg incubation. Past studies have successfully cultured FSSC from the nest sand and debris from nest surroundings (Rosado-Rodríguez and Maldonado-Ramírez, 2016; Siti Nordahliawate et al., 2017). However, the ubiquitous nature of FSSC (Zhang et al., 2006) implies that successful infection depends on the extent of natural nests

experiencing environmental stressors such as tidal inundation and unsuitable substrate's sizes (Sarmiento-Ramírez et al., 2014). One unintended anthropogenic stressor may be the re-establishment of nests in hatcheries, and little is known how this contributes to disease occurrence.

In Peninsular Malaysia, sea turtle eggs laid at natural nesting beaches are mostly relocated to the nearest ex-situ hatchery to reduce poaching (Mortimer et al., 1993; Chan, 2006). However, this raises the issue of whether the continual reuse of the same sand within the fenced hatchery for several nesting seasons may result in accumulation of FSSC. This may be the reason behind the recent discovery of STEF in some hatcheries (Siti Nordahliawate et al., 2017). We hypothesized that microbial community and FSSC abundance in the sand of egg chamber in hatchery which reused sand differed with natural nesting beach. In this study, we investigated if FSSC could be identified from diseased eggs across sea turtle hatcheries of Peninsular Malaysia. We profiled and contrasted the microbial composition of sands collected in hatcheries and their residing nesting beaches. Together, this part of the study discloses microbiome changes contributed by hatchery practices and offers new insights to inform conservation practices in sea turtles.

2.2 Methodology

Samples such as 63 *Fusarium*-infected dead eggs and 123 sand samples (63 hatchery sands and 60 beach (control) sands) were collected from seven sea turtle hatcheries in Peninsular Malaysia (Figure 2). Symptoms of *Fusarium*-infected eggs are shown in Figure 1. Eggshells from *Fusarium*-infected dead eggs were rinsed with sterilized water to remove sand particles, cut into approximately 1 x 1 cm, and incubated on Potato Dextrose Agar with 50 µg/mL chloramphenicol at 30 °C. Subcultures were made on the same medium until pure culture was obtained. DNA extraction and amplification of all isolates using primer pairs SR6R/ITS4 (Irinnyi et al., 2016), which targets the nrDNA internal transcribed region, LR0R/LR6 (Rehner and Samuels 1994; Sarmiento-Ramírez et al., 2014; Vilgalys and Hester 1990), which targets the region on large subunit of the ribosomal DNA, and fRPB2-7cF/fRPB2-

11aR (Liu et al., 1999), which targets the RNA polymerase II (RPB2) gene region were performed. Then, multilocus phylogenetic analysis based on these regions was carried out. For sand samples, total gDNA extraction and amplicon generation were carried out using tagged primer pairs V3/V4 (Kozich et al., 2013) and ITS3ngs(mix)/ITS4 (Tedersoo et al., 2014) for bacterial 16S rRNA and fungal internal transcribed spacer (ITS) amplicons respectively. Then, amplicon samples proceeded with normalization, library preparation, and sequenced with Illumina MiSeq with paired-end 2 x 300 bp chemistry.

Sequence data were processed as follow: barcode demultiplexing, adaptor and primer sequences trimmed, forward and reverse reads were filtered and merged. Operational taxonomic unit (OTU) was clustered at 97 % sequence identity. Taxonomy classification of OTU was performed against RDP training set (v16) and UNITE database (v7.1) for 16S and ITS reads respectively using the SINTAX algorithm (Edgar, 2016; Edgar, 2018). Amplicon data were analyzed with phyloseq package (v1.28.0; McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) in RStudio. For beta diversity analysis, OTUs that appeared less than three times in at least 20 % of all samples were filtered from the analysis. Distances between samples were calculated using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. Heatmap was plotted using pheatmap package (v1.0.12; Kolde, 2015) with distance measure using “correlation” option to perform samples clustering. Differentially abundant taxa were determined using DESeq2 (v1.24; Love et al., 2014) at genus and OTU level for bacterial and fungal amplicons, respectively.

Figure 2: Map, location and metadata of the sampled sea turtle hatcheries and neighbouring beaches in Peninsular Malaysia. Mean hatching success were calculated from sampled nests only. *Asterisk denotes which samples were collected from total failed nest only. TH, turtle hatchery; SEATRU, Sea Turtle Research Unit, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu; WWF, World Wide Fund for Nature, Malaysia; DoF, Department of Fisheries Malaysia.

2.3 Results

To determine the effect of reusing sand on microbiota structure and pathogens' abundance, we sampled *Fusarium*-infected unhatched eggs and sand samples (hatchery sands and beach (control) sands) from seven sea turtle hatcheries across Peninsular Malaysia (Figure 2). Among the hatcheries, Penarik (P) site relocates to new location every nesting season, which makes it the only hatchery which does not reuse the same sand for egg incubation. All sampled nests contained unhatched eggs with symptoms of fungal colonization as described (Figure 1; Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2010). Upon molecular characterization of fungi isolated, a total of 82 isolates were obtained and *Fusarium* spp. were identified from all sampled hatcheries (Figure 3). Of these, 68 (82.9 %) were *F. falciforme*, 12 (14.6 %) were *F. keratoplasticum*, one *F. oxysporum*, and one *Fusarium* species.

Figure 3: Bootstrap consensus phylogenetic tree of *Fusarium* isolates by IQ-TREE analysis, inferred from combined ITS, 28S nrDNA and RPB2 sequence data. Bootstrap value supporting the branch is based on 1000 replicates.

Distinct microbial community structure between beach and hatchery sands

Overall, sand microbiota in sea turtle nesting beaches and hatcheries were composed of 7,267 bacterial and 3,229 fungal OTUs. Phyla compositions of bacteria and fungi were similar across all sand types (Figure 4). Bacterial species richness and community evenness were lower in hatcheries than nesting beach sands (Figure 5). The nesting beaches had on average 764.5 fewer bacterial OTUs than the hatcheries. The most dominating bacterial phylum across all samples was *Proteobacteria* (averaging 36.6%), followed by unclassified bacteria (15.4%) and *Firmicutes* (13.3%). Most bacterial phyla were significantly different in relative abundance across sand types (Figure 6). In particular, *Bacteroidetes* was almost twice as abundant in hatcheries (13.3%) than nesting beaches (5.7%). This was due to an elevated *Bacteroidetes* relative abundance of over 20% in four nests from three hatcheries (MH2, MH3, SH1, and RH1; Appendix 3), but no single *Bacteroidetes* OTU was responsible for the increased proportion. In the case of fungi, the phylum Ascomycota had the highest mean relative abundance (37.7%), consistent with the frequent observation of dominant fungal species present in soil communities (Egidi *et al.*, 2019), followed by unclassified fungi (36.4%) and Basidiomycota (22.3%). In contrast to the bacterial community, hatchery sand harboured a higher fungal richness but lower community evenness (Figure 5). The hatcheries had on average 193.7 more fungal OTUs than the beach. Mean relative abundances of four major fungal phyla were similar between sand types (Figure 6). Together these suggest large inter- and intra-site variation.

(A) 16S

(B) ITS

Figure 4: Bar plots of bacterial (A) and fungal (B) relative composition in all samples at the phylum level. First and second alphabet in Sample ID represents site code and sand type (B: Beach; H: Hatchery), respectively. *Asterisks indicate samples contained high proportion of *Inocybe* sp..

(A) 16S

(B) ITS

Figure 5: Alpha diversity measures of bacterial (A) and fungal (B) community in different sand types. Statistical significance was calculated using unpaired-Wilcoxon test between sand types for each measure (ns: $P > 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$; *** $P \leq 0.001$; **** $P \leq 0.0001$).

(A) 16S

Figure 6: Box plots of bacterial (A) and fungal (B) relative composition of different sand types at the phylum level. Each dot represents one sample. Only the top eight major bacterial phyla are shown in (A). Statistical significance was calculated using unpaired-Wilcoxon test between sand types for each phylum (ns: $P > 0.05$; * $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$; *** $P \leq 0.001$).

Microbial communities of sand samples were significantly different between hatcheries and nesting beaches (Figure 7). Compared to other hatcheries which reused sand, P hatchery stood out as it changes location every season and had exhibited similar bacterial community to the nearby nesting beach (Figure 8). Statistical tests showed significant difference in bacterial composition between hatcheries and nesting beaches (after removing P hatchery sands; ANOSIM $R = 0.92$, $P = 0.001$; PERMANOVA $R^2 = 0.36$, $P < 0.001$; betadisper $P = 0.2$). In the case of fungal community, samples consisted high proportion of *Inocybe* sp. were separated from beach and hatchery sand clusters (Figure 7; Figure 8). PC1 (21.3 %) set apart these samples while PC2 (15.4 %) separated hatcheries and nesting beaches. After excluding these samples, similar conclusion was also drawn from the fungal community that significant dispersion and composition was observed between sand types (after removing samples with high relative abundance of *Inocybe* sp.; ANOSIM $R = 0.79$, $P = 0.001$; PERMANOVA $R^2 = 0.18$, $P < 0.001$; betadisper $P = 0.001$).

Figure 7: Principal Coordinate Analysis plots measured by Bray-Curtis distance of (A) bacterial and (B) fungal communities. Each dot represents one site and different colour denote sand type. Ellipses represent 95 % confidence interval within each category (hatchery or nesting beach). Multivariate statistical analyses ANOSIM and PERMANOVA were used to test the community differences between sand types. *Asterisk denote a subset of samples containing high relative abundance of *Inocybe* sp..

Figure 8: Principal Coordinate Analysis plots measured by Bray-Curtis distance of (A) bacterial and (B) fungal communities. Each dot represents one sample and different color denote sampling site. Multivariate statistical analyses ANOSIM and PERMANOVA were used to test the community differences between sand types. *Asterisk denote a subset of samples containing high relative abundance of *Inocybe* sp..

Differentially abundant taxa in hatchery sands

Relative abundances of the top ten major bacterial or fungal taxa clustered the samples based on sand type – except for hatchery P, which grouped with nesting beaches (Figure 9). The FSSC pathogens, *Pseudallescheria boydii*, and an unclassified fungus (OTU5) were present in high abundances in all hatcheries except for P. The public database matched OTU5 to the order *Capnodiales*, which contains fungal species that are plant pathogens (Crous *et al.*, 2009). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was most frequently detected in the S and M nesting beaches. Interestingly, nesting beach S had a relatively higher abundance of various *Bacillus* spp. (mean 9.7% vs. 7.2% average in all samples) and FSSC (3.0% vs. 1.4%) compared to other nesting beaches.

Analysis of differentially abundant taxa through DESeq2 analysis revealed that hatchery sand had 168 bacterial genera and 54 fungal OTUs significantly higher in hatchery sand (Figure 10; Figure 11). Conversely, nesting beaches harboured 89 and 100 higher abundance of bacterial genera and fungal OTUs, respectively. The aforementioned *P. boydii* and *Capnodiales* sp. were indeed significantly more abundant in the hatcheries ($P = 4.3e^{-15}$ and $5.8e^{-11}$, respectively). Interestingly, FSSC was not significantly more abundant in hatcheries ($P = 0.5$). Upon closer inspection, FSSC also exhibited relatively high proportions in the beach sand of sites S (mean 3.0%) and C (mean 2.4%), implying that this fungal group can be high abundance in nature.

Higher abundance of FSSC and *P. boydii* in reused sand

FSSC had a higher mean relative abundance in hatcheries than nesting beaches (excluding hatchery P; unpaired-Wilcoxon test, nesting beach vs. hatchery, 1.3% vs. 5.2%, $P = 0.0015$; Figure 12). Of all the *Fusarium* species detected, FSSC comprised 94.9% of all *Fusarium* sequences in the hatcheries. *P. boydii* also showed higher mean relative abundance in hatcheries (excluding hatchery P; unpaired-Wilcoxon test, nesting beach vs. hatchery, 0.3% vs. 11.5%, $P = 7.1e^{-10}$). *P. boydii* was found to be consistently higher in abundance across hatcheries (most samples are at least > 5%) and on average 6.4% higher than FSSC.

Figure 9: Heatmap of relative abundance (%) of top ten major bacterial and fungal OTUs from each site totalling 33 OTUs. Colour in each box denote the mean relative abundance of OTU in corresponding sites. F, fungal; B, bacterial.

Figure 10: DESeq2 analysis of differentially abundant bacterial genera in different sand types. The plot shows representative taxa with log₂ fold change < -5 and > 5 only. Each dot denotes one genus.

Figure 11: DESeq2 analysis of differentially abundant fungal OTUs in different sand types. Each dot denotes one OTU.

Figure 12: Boxplots showing relative abundance (%) of *Fusarium solani* species complex and *Pseudallescheria boydii* between two sand types. Statistical significance was calculated using unpaired-Wilcoxon test (** $P \leq 0.01$; **** $P \leq 0.0001$). Samples from hatchery P were removed from analysis due to evidently different community structures with other hatchery sand samples.

2.4 Discussion

Previous reports have shown that fungal pathogens present in nesting beaches can infect sea turtle eggs and cause massive mortalities (Phillott *et al.*, 2004; Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014). Relocated eggs that come into contact with sand can also be contaminated (Phillott and Parmenter, 2001a; Patino-Martinez *et al.*, 2011; Siti Nordahliawate *et al.*, 2017). To determine if reusing sand has an effect on disease prevalence, we determined the relative differences in microbial composition and FSSC abundance in sand across seven sea turtle hatcheries and neighbouring nesting beaches in Peninsular Malaysia. Our findings revealed that all hatcheries that practiced sand reuse shared a microbiota that was clearly different from those of neighbouring nesting beaches. By relocating hatchery (i.e. not reusing sand), hatchery P exhibited the lowest relative abundance of FSSC and at the same time, had highest hatching success of the hatchery nests when compared to other hatcheries. We also qualitatively observed fewer eggs that exhibited STEF symptoms in hatchery P. Nonetheless, as sample replication cannot be performed at site P, additional surveys should be carried out to strengthen the current results. In addition, higher abundances of several *Bacillus* spp. and FSSC were observed in the nesting beaches of hatchery S, the only *in-situ* hatchery sampled in this study. One possible explanation is that high nesting turnouts altered the microbiota more drastically in a short nesting beach (approximately 350 m) with high nesting density (mean of 1,150 nests per year; Chan, 2010).

The enclosed hatchery area may be a nutrient-rich environment for potential pathogens to cultivate. Similar scenarios have been observed for other fungal diseases in animals and plants. The fungal pathogen that causes white-nose syndrome in bats, *Pseudogymnoascus destructans*, was detected in the soil of ground environments where the bats hibernate (Lindner *et al.*, 2011). In crop fields, pathogens of *Fusarium* spp. were shown to continue their necrotrophic life cycle in crop residues or debris, which then serve as sources of inoculum in the following season (Cobo-Díaz *et al.*, 2019). Reusage of sand will thus become a reservoir for FSSC or other potential pathogens to accumulate and infect eggs in subsequent

nesting seasons. Our assessment of microbial abundance was determined post-hatchling emergence and nest excavation to avoid egg disturbance. Hence, the relative abundance of FSSC in hatcheries was a result of infection *a posteriori*. A more detailed assessment of FSSC abundance beginning from oviposition, incubation and up to nest excavation should provide a clearer understanding on STEF establishment. A previous study suggested that fungal hyphae spread from diseased eggs to adjacent viable eggs (Phillott and Parmenter, 2001a), signifying that initial establishment is key to successful infection. Initial fungal density could be reduced by applying suitable sand treatments to increase hatching success (Bézy *et al.*, 2015). However, turtle hatcheries should consider space, cost, and labour constraints to decide if this is feasible.

FSSC is commonly found in the environment (Zhang *et al.*, 2006), and has been found along with other *Fusarium* species in natural nesting beaches. We detected a higher abundance of FSSC across hatcheries and in some of the nesting beaches, suggesting that additional factors may contribute to the overall accumulation of this species complex. Differences in the geographical distribution of *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* were observed. Previous reports in some of the main sea turtle nesting beaches in the Indian and Atlantic Oceans have shown that *F. keratoplasticum* is predominant (Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014; Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2017), but the current study and a recent survey (Siti Nordahliawate *et al.*, 2017) found a higher isolation frequency of *F. falciforme* in Malaysia. More studies on differences in environmental factors are needed to understand the prevalence of pathogenic species across these nesting regions. Our study further revealed different abundances in FSSC species across Peninsular Malaysia. Of the hatcheries surveyed, only the Melaka (M) hatchery had a higher relative abundance of *F. keratoplasticum* (~ 5% of sequences; data not shown) and higher isolation frequency (Siti Nordahliawate *et al.*, 2017). The origin *F. keratoplasticum* in these environments has been associated with human activities (Zhang *et al.*, 2006), but whether this was the true source is unclear, as all sampled hatcheries have restricted access.

Various studies have shown that both FSSC and *P. boydii* are frequently found in fungal-infected sea turtle eggs (Phillott *et al.*, 2001; Sarmiento-Ramírez *et al.*, 2017). Co-occurrence of these two fungi and the higher prevalence of the latter suggest that *P. boydii* is a more sensitive biomarker for identifying FSSC-contaminated nest and possibly a fungal pathogen for sea turtle eggs. To date, it has not been proven that *P. boydii* infects sea turtle eggs, but it has been shown to infect veterinary animals (Elad, 2011). A high relative abundance of *P. boydii* was detected in hatchery nests that reused sand, and this warrant further investigation of the species' role in the infection. Interestingly, our co-occurrence network analyses suggest that FSSC and *P. boydii* did not directly interact. This may also suggest that the high occurrence of *P. boydii* may be a post-effect of FSSC infection. Since *P. boydii* is a common soil microbe (Gilgado *et al.*, 2005) and an opportunist pathogen that causes chronic diseases in human (Travis *et al.*, 1985; Gilgado *et al.*, 2005), we speculate that FSSC infects turtle eggs and *P. boydii* uses the nutrients from dead eggs to proliferate in mass.

2.5 Conclusion

This study delineated the microbiota and quantified FSSC abundance in the nests of sea turtle hatcheries. Our key findings indicated that STEF was most probably heightened from the practice of reusing sand for egg incubation. The consequence of such result suggests that both turtle eggs and hatchery staffs suffer an increased risk of the infection by FSSC or other opportunistic microbes. Hence, we recommend sea turtle hatchery to change sand after every nesting season in order to maximize hatchling productions by reducing the potential pathogen inoculum. This work emphasizes that stringency in hatchery management must be maintained for the efforts of conservation to not be in vain. For disease control and prevention, future attention needs to be paid to on the causes and consequences of abundances and interactions of microbes at different stages of infection not just in nests but also the nesting beaches due to rapid changing environments.

Chapter 3: Comparative genomics of *Fusarium solani* species complex

3.1 Introduction

Comparative genomic analyses of several *Fusarium* species have revealed genomic features which are associated with pathogenicity. Similar to other pathogenic fungi, the genome of *Fusarium* consists of two compartments: the core chromosomes (CC) and the accessory chromosomes (AC). The CCs mostly contain the housekeeping genes that are vital for survival and are responsible for essential functions such as primary metabolism and reproduction. On the other hand, the ACs contain mostly genes which aids in niche adaptation and pathogenicity (Ma *et al.*, 2013). For instance, ACs of pathogenic *Fusarium* species were of particular interests due to several characteristics that are different compared to CCs. ACs of pathogenic *Fusarium* species contain genes which are lineage-specific (Coleman *et al.*, 2009; Ma *et al.*, 2010; Eva-Maria Niehaus *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2020) and host-specific (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). These host-specific genes are specifically expressed during infection of its specialized plant hosts (Cuomo *et al.*, 2007; Ma *et al.*, 2010; Ma *et al.*, 2013). ACs of pathogenic strain of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* was experimentally proven to be able to horizontally transfer to the non-pathogenic strain and transformed it into pathogen (Ma *et al.*, 2010). In addition, ACs also contain genes encode for secondary metabolites which involve in functions that includes toxin production, virulence against host, and secreted effectors (Ma *et al.*, 2013). These characteristics are believed to enhance its advantages in being a pathogen due to its ability in niche adaptation.

One of the extensively-studied species and the first published genome within the FSSC was the *Nectria haematococca* (teleomorph of *Fusarium solani*; MPVI isolate 77-13-4; Coleman *et al.*, 2009). This species is commonly found in the environment as saprophyte and as pathogen for plants and animals. Three ACs (Chromosome 14, 15, 17) were determined in the genome of *F. solani*, which have features such as lower GC content, higher repeat density, and enriched in unique genes that has lower average gene size compared to CCs (Coleman *et al.*, 2009). The structural

characteristics of genome in most pathogenic fungi are mainly differentiate into two compartments – the core chromosome (CC), which contain essential genes required for survival and reproduction; and accessory chromosome (AC), which is repeat-rich and contain enriched genes mostly associated to niche adaptation and pathogenicity (refs). ACs, sometimes referred as accessory, conditionally dispensable, and supernumerary chromosome, can be dispensable and did not affect the fungal growth, proven in several *Fusarium* species such as *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopercisi* (Ma et al., 2010) and *F. vanettenii* (previously *Nectria haematococca*). The ACs of *F. vanettenii* harbours pea-specific pathogenic genes – the PEP cluster, which confer virulence on pea plants (Wasmann & VanEtten, 1996; Han et al., 2001; Temporini & VanEtten, 2002). Hence, AC with virulence genes is also referred as pathogenicity chromosome (Ma et al., 2013). Virulence genes on AC were validated *in planta*. For example, PEP cluster of *F. vanettenii* isolate MPVI 77-13-4 is located on its ACs, which contain pisatin demethylase (PDA1) gene functions as phytoalexin pisatin detoxification. Upon deletion of the gene or the whole AC, reduced its virulence on garden pea (Wasmann and VanEtten, 1996; Coleman, 2016). It is unclear whether any of these virulence genes were present in other FSSC species, whether they also played a role during animal infection and whether any novel genes involved in animal pathogenicity were also enriched on ACs.

By comparing with the first published FSSC genome, this part of the study will be carried out to explore the basis genomic features and diversity of pathogenic mechanisms in FSSC strains from multi-kingdom hosts, especially those that are pathogenic towards animals in comparison to plants. Specifically, the similarities and differences of these pathogenic features will be compared. Then, putative genes involve in disease development of animals by FSSC will be determined.

3.2 Methodology

Species identification of isolates.

DNA isolation of seven days *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) mycelium cultures was carried out using ZYMO Quick-DNA Fungal/Bacterial

Miniprep Kit (ZYMO Research, Irvine, CA, USA, Cat. #D6005). The identity of these isolates was determined by multilocus sequence typing (MLST) of ITS rDNA (ITS5), RPB2 (7cF/11aR), and TEF1 (EF1/EF2) regions (O' Donnell et al., 2008 Molecular), incorporating other FSSC sequences which were phylogenetically determined (Geiser et al. 2020, phylogenomic; **Table 1**). PCR conditions and phylogenetic analysis were performed as described in Hoh et al., (2020).

No.	Species	Strain	Haplotype	NCBI Accession number			Note
				ITS rDNA	RPB2	TEF1	
1	<i>Fusarium illudens</i>	NRRL 22090	-	AF178393	EU329488	AF178326	FSSC Clade 1, Outgroup
2	<i>Fusarium plagianthi</i>	NRRL 22632	-	AF178417	EU329519	AF178354	FSSC Clade 1, Outgroup
3	<i>Fusarium cyanescens</i>	NRRL 37625	FSSC 27	LR583712	LR583827	LR583606	
4	<i>Fusarium spathulatum</i>	NRRL 28541	FSSC 26	EU329674	EU329542	DQ246882	
5	<i>Fusarium macrosporium</i>	CBS 142424	-	LT1746266	LT1746331	LT1746218	
6	<i>Fusarium ferrugineum</i>	NRRL 32437	FSSC 28	DQ094446	EU329581	DQ246979	
7	<i>Fusarium oblongum</i>	NRRL 28008	FSSC 29	LR583746	LR583853	LR583631	
8	<i>Fusarium petrotiphilum</i>	NRRL 13952, CBS 203.32	FSSC 1	DQ094320	LR583857	DQ246835	
9	<i>Fusarium parceramosum</i>	CBS 115695	FSSC 18	JX435199	JX435249	JX435149	
10	<i>Fusarium pseudotokinense</i>	CBS 143038	-	LR583758	LR583867	LR583640	
11	<i>Fusarium bostrycooides</i>	CBS 144.25	FSSC 25	LR583704	LR583818	LR583597	
12	<i>Fusarium quercinum</i>	NRRL 22652	FSSC 14	LR583760	LR583869	DQ247634	
13	<i>Fusarium mori</i>	NRRL 22230	FSSC 17	AF178420	EU329499	AF178358	
14	<i>Fusarium breve</i>	CBS 144387	FSSC 15	LR583708	LR583822	LR583601	
15	<i>Fusarium vanettenii</i>	NRRL 45880, MPVI 77-13-4	FSSC 11	LR583753	LR583862	LR583636	
16	<i>Fusarium waltergamsii</i>	NRRL 32323	FSSC 7	DQ094420	EU329576	DQ246951	
17	<i>Fusarium metavorans</i>	NRRL 43489	FSSC 6	DQ790528	DQ790572	DQ790484	
18	<i>Fusarium suttonianum</i>	NRRL 32858	FSSC 20	DQ094617	EU329630	DQ247163	
19	<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	CBS 475.67	FSSC 3+4	MG189935	LT960558	LT960669	
20	<i>Fusarium keratoplasticum</i>	FRC S-2477	FSSC 2	NR130690	JN235897	JN235712	
21	<i>Fusarium solani</i>	NRRL 66304, CBS 140079	FSSC 5	KT313633	KT313623	KT313611	
22	<i>Fusarium bataticola</i>	NRRL 22402	FSSC 23	DQ094304	FJ240381	AF178344	
23	<i>Fusarium tonkinense</i>	NRRL 32755	FSSC 9	DQ094534	EU329613	DQ247073	
24	<i>Fusarium crassum</i>	CBS 144386	FSSC 34	LR583709	LR583823	LR583604	
25	<i>Fusarium ambrosium</i>	NRRL 20438	FSSC 19	DQ094315	JX171584	AF178332	
26	<i>Fusarium floridanum</i>	AF-3, NRRL 62628	-	KC691563	KC691653	KC691535	
27	<i>Fusarium oligoseptatum</i>	AF-4, NRRL 62579	-	KC691566	KC691656	KC691538	
28	<i>Fusarium kuroshium</i>	AF-12, NRRL 62945	-	KM406636	KM406649	KM406629	
29	<i>Fusarium pseudensiforme</i>	NRRL 46517, CBS 125729	FSSC 33	KC691584	KC691645	DQ247512	
30	<i>Fusarium riograndense</i>	CMF 12570	-	KT186366	KX534003	KX534002	
31	<i>Fusarium lichenicola</i>	NRRL 28030	FSSC 16	DQ094355	KR674002	DQ246877	
32	<i>Fusarium neocosmosporiellum</i>	NRRL 22166	FSSC 8	DQ094319	EU329497	AF178350	
33	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC 12	NRRL 54721	FSSC 12	JQ743210	JQ743212	JQ743208	
34	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC 12	NRRL 54979	FSSC 12	KC808244	KC808342	KC808202	
35	<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	Fu3	FSSC 3+4				Sequence generated by this study
36	<i>Fusarium keratoplasticum</i>	Fu6	FSSC 2				Sequence generated by this study
37	<i>Fusarium keratoplasticum</i>	LHS11	FSSC 2				Sequence generated by this study
38	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC 12	LHS14	FSSC 12				Sequence generated by this study
39	<i>Fusarium vanettenii</i>	Fs6	FSSC 11				Sequence generated by this study
40	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	Ph1	-				Sequence generated by this study

Table 1: *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) sequences used in multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) phylogenetic tree.

Nucleic acids isolation, genome and transcriptome sequencing.

After species identification through MLST, six isolates from FSSC clade 3 were chosen for genome sequencing and comparative analyses. The genomes contained species includes two *F. keratoplasticum* (isolate Fu6 and LHS11), one *F. falciforme* (Fu3), one *Fusarium* sp. (Ph1), one *F. vanettenii* (Fs6) and one *Fusarium* sp. haplotype FSSC12 (LHS14). Pure cultures of these strains were incubated on ½ Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) at 28 °C for seven days and mycelium were scraped off from the culture media for gDNA and RNA isolation. Genomic DNA was extracted following protocols designed for high-molecular-weight gDNA sequencing (Mayjonade et al., 2016) and size selection and purification of isolated gDNA was performed following Chouikh et al., (1979). The integrity of gDNA were evaluated using Fragment Analyzer 5200 (Advanced Analytic Technologies, Inc., Ankeny, IA, USA) and the fragment lengths were determined using PROsize 2 software (Advanced Analytic Technologies, Inc., Ankeny, IA, USA). Genomes were sequenced using both Illumina and Oxford Nanopore platforms. Detailed information such as sequencing platforms, library kits used and sequence accession number for each sample can be found on **Table 2**. The read summary of DNA sequencing data is shown in **Table 3**. For gene model prediction and annotation, RNA of the six isolates were extracted following the TRIzol reagent protocol (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #15596026). Integrity of the isolated RNA was checked using 1.5 % agarose gel and quantity was determined using Invitrogen Qubit® 4 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) before library preparation and sequencing.

Species	Strain	Nucleic acid	Sequencing platform	Number of runs	Flowcell type	Library kit	NCBI accession number
<i>F. falciforme</i>	Fu3	gDNA	Nanopore MinION	2	FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK108-long; SQK-DCS108	
		DNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	KAPA Library Preparation Kit-Illumina KK8201	
		RNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	TruSeq Stranded mRNA Library Prep	
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	Fu6	gDNA	Nanopore MinION	3	FLO-MIN107, FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK308; SQK-DCS108	
		DNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	KAPA Library Preparation Kit-Illumina KK8201	
		RNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	TruSeq Stranded mRNA Library Prep	
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	LHS11	gDNA	Nanopore MinION	1	FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK108	
		DNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	KAPA Library Preparation Kit-Illumina KK8201	
		RNA				NA, used Fu6 transcripts for gene model prediction	
<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC12	LHS14	gDNA	Nanopore MinION	1	FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK108	
		DNA	Illumina HiSeq	1	-	KAPA Library Preparation Kit-Illumina KK8201	
		RNA	Illumina NovaSeq	1	-	NEB Next(R) Ultra RNA Library Prep Kit	
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	Ph1	gDNA	Nanopore GridION	1	FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK109	
		DNA	Illumina NovaSeq	2	-	NEB Next(R) Ultra DNA Library Prep Kit	
		RNA	Illumina NovaSeq	1	-	NEB Next(R) Ultra RNA Library Prep Kit	
<i>F. vanettenii</i>	Fs6	gDNA	Nanopore GridION	1	FLO-MIN106	SQK-LSK109	
		DNA	Illumina NovaSeq	1	-	NEB Next(R) Ultra DNA Library Prep Kit	
		RNA	Illumina NovaSeq	1	-	NEB Next(R) Ultra RNA Library Prep Kit	

Table 2: *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) sequences used in multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) phylogenetic tree.

Species	Strain	Read type	Read length	Number of runs	Basecalling method	Library size (bp)	Number of reads	Coverage
<i>F. falciforme</i>	Fu3	Nanopore	1000-280335	2	guppy v3.2.4	6681985122	879682	107.93
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-			79.55
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	Fu6	Nanopore	172-175973	3	albacore 2.2.7	2923865869	399938	51.71
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-			51.39
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	LHS11	Nanopore	1000-460088	1	guppy v3.2.4	7272748077	500842	137.44
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-			35.39
FSSC12	LHS14	Nanopore	1000-243742	1	guppy v3.2.4	8841392932	1160307	118.02
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-			29.58
<i>F. solani</i>	Ph1	Nanopore	1000-176316	1	guppy v4.0.11	9825360402	795746	192.88
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-			55.03
<i>F. vanettenii</i>	Fs6	Nanopore	1000-210975	1	guppy v4.0.11	10504078463	664915	118.68
		Illumina	150bp PE	1	-	3140460300	20936402	42.98

Table 3: Read summary of genome assemblies from each sequencing platform. Genome coverage was calculated based on median coverage in 10kb window.

Genome assembly and annotations.

Guppy or albacore (see **Table 3**) were used to perform basecalling of Nanopore raw signals and assembled using Flye (Kolmogorov et al., 2019) and further polish and correct the assembled sequences with consensus mapped reads from Illumina using Pilon (v1.22). Lastly, assemblies were generated using HaploMerger2 (ver. 20180603). Annotation of repeat elements of the genomes was performed following Berriman et al., (2018) except described otherwise in the following: a consensus repeat library was created using repeat elements identified via RepeatModeler (v. open-1.0.8; <https://www.repeatmasker.org/RepeatModeler/>) and TransposonPSI (release 08222010; <http://transposonpsi.sourceforge.net>) and merged using usearch (v8.1.1861; Edgar, 2010). RepeatMasker (v. open-4.0.7; option -s; <https://www.repeatmasker.org>) was used to mask the predicted repeat regions in each genome. Telomeric repeats of each scaffold were determined using Tandem Repeat Finder (v4.09; default parameters; Benson, 1999). Enriched hexamers were identified (TTAGGG) manually on the terminal 5 kb regions of each scaffold to confirm the presence of telomeres. Genes of the assemblies were predicted using Augustus (v3.2.1) and trained with BRAKER2 (option fungi and softmasked). MAKER2 (v2.31.9) was then used to combine evidence from the assembled transcripts, reference proteomes, and transcript evidence obtained from RNA-seq of the mycelium to produce a final gene annotation set. Completeness of each genomes was assessed by BUSCO (v5.2.2; Manni et al., 2021; **Table 4**). Functional annotations of the amino acid sequences were carried out using eggNOG-mapper v2 (<http://eggnog-mapper.embl.de>; default parameters; Cantalapiedra et al., 2021) on eggNOG v5 database (Huerta-Cepas et al., 2019). Protein domains and families were identified using pfam_scan.pl (v1.6; <http://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/Pfam/Tools/>) on Pfam database (release 34.0; Mistry et al., 2021). Additional annotations were carried out as follows: carbohydrates active enzymes were determined using dbCAN2 (v2.0.11; Zhang et al., 2018); secondary metabolites detection via antiSMASH (v6.0; Blin et al., 2021); and fungal effectors were predicted using EffectorP (v3.0; Sperschneider & Dodds,

2021) on amino acid sequences which passed the signal peptide prediction via signalP (v6.0; Teufel et al., 2021).

Orthology and phylogenomic analyses.

Orthology analysis was performed via OrthoFinder (v2.3.8; Emms & Kelly, 2019) using six genome assemblies created from this study, 17 other *Fusarium* assemblies from databases and an outgroup species *Beauveria bassiana* (**Table 5**). A total of 2,385 single-copy orthogroups (OGs) were determined and sequence from each of the OG were sent to RAxML-NG for maximum likelihood phylogeny inference (v0.9.0; option --model LG+I+F+G4, --bs-trees 100; Kozlov et al., 2019). All trees and bootstraps-supported replicates generated from the previous step were combined for genome-wide species tree construction using ASTRAL-III (v5.7.7; option -r 100; Rabiee et al., 2019) and visualised using FigTree (v1.4.4; Rambaut, 2018).

Species	<i>F. falciforme</i>	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC12	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	<i>F. vanettenii</i>
Assembly abbreviation	Fu3	Fu6	LHS11	LHS14	Ph1	Fs6
Genome size	53,563,088	49,462,855	53,490,075	56,318,919	51,460,811	77,440,244
Number of sequences	14	25	26	35	24	65
Largest scaffold (base)	6,821,300	6,472,136	6,638,608	6,191,652	5,428,158	6,793,905
N50	3,875,999	4,213,465	3,498,532	3,818,207	3,298,798	3,359,130
L50	6	5	6	6	6	9
N90	2,721,497	2,285,016	1,533,782	923,312	1,139,675	903,371
L90	12	11	13	14	17	26
GC %	49.38	51.25	51.35	48.55	51.06	50.32
Number of protein coding genes	15,124	14,927	15,044	15,929	15,493	19,146
Protein BUSCO % (fungi_odb10)	99.0	98.4	98.4	98.3	100	98.7
Protein BUSCO % (ascomycota_odb10)	98.8	98.8	98.1	98.6	99.8	98.7

Table 4: Genome statistics of six sequenced isolates of *Fusarium solani* species complex.

Species complex	Species	Abbreviation in this study	Strain	Assembly name	Genome size	No. of scaffolds	N50	L50	No. of genes	Isolation source	Country	Literature reference	Sequence source	
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	Fu6	Fu6		49,462,855	25	4,213,465	5	14,927	Hawksbill sea turtle (<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>) egg	Malaysia	This study		
	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i>	LHS11	LHS11		53,490,075	26	3,498,532	6	15,044	Harbour seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)	Taiwan			
	<i>F. falciforme</i>	Fu3	Fu3		53,563,088	14	3,875,999	6	15,124	Hawksbill sea turtle (<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>) egg	Malaysia			
	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	Ph1	Ph1		51,460,811	24	3,225,437	7	15,493	Orchid (<i>Phalaenopsis</i> sp.)	Taiwan			
	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. FSSC12	LHS14	LHS14		56,318,919	35	3,818,207	6	15,929	Roughtail stingray (<i>Bathytoshia centroura</i>)	Taiwan			
	<i>F. vanettenii</i>	Fs6	Fs6		77,440,244	65	3,359,130	9	19,146	Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)	Taiwan			
	<i>F. vanettenii</i>	FVANE	mpVI 77-13-4	Necha2.v2	51,286,497	209	1,255,602	10	15,708	Pea x soil cross	USA	Coleman et al., 2009	NCBI	
	<i>F. solani</i>	FSSC5	MPI-SDFR-AT-0091	Fusso1.v1	52,932,111	74	2,221,287	9	17,656	NA	NA	JGI	JGI	
	<i>F. ambrosium</i>	-	NRRL 20438	NRRL20438v1	49,042,336	1,366	121,643	120	17,420	Insect head	India	NA	NCBI	NCBI
	<i>F. floridanum</i>	-	NRRL 62606	NRRL62606.SPAdes	47,429,815	1,719	59,505	234	16,934	<i>Euvallacea interjectus</i>	USA Florida	NA	NCBI	NCBI
	<i>F. kuroshium</i>	-	AF-12; UCR3666	Fus_sp_AF-12_v1.0	46,636,844	1,403	91,081	158	16,661	<i>Persea americana</i>	USA California	NA	NCBI	NCBI
	<i>F. oligoseptatum</i>	-	AF-4; NRRL 62579	NRRL62579.SPAdes	48,659,138	1,171	158,082	93	17,740	<i>Euvallacea validus</i>	USA Pennsylvania	NA	NCBI	NCBI
	<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	-	AF-6; NRRL 62590	NRRL62590.SPAdes	43,121,288	-	69,814	187	15,274	<i>Euvallacea</i> sp.	USA Florida	NA	NCBI	NCBI
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	-	AF-8; NRRL 62584	NRRL62584.SPAdes	47,520,037	1,006	168,109	81	16,432	<i>Euvallacea</i> sp.	USA Florida	NA	NCBI	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium heterosporum</i>	<i>F. graminum</i>	-	NRRL 20692	ASM1326616v1	34,983,573	977	85,760	124	11,163	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Ethiopia	Kim et al., 2020	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium lateritium</i>	<i>F. sarcochroum</i>	-	NRRL 20472	ASM1326618v1	46,449,918	1,849	55,061	254	14,827	<i>Viscum album</i>	Switzerland	Kim et al., 2020	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium staphyleae</i>	<i>F. zealandicum</i>	-	NRRL 22465	ASM1326619v1	33,536,579	1,836	43,137	241	10,733	NA	NA	Kim et al., 2020	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	<i>F. albosuccineum</i>	-	NRRL 20459	ASM1293199v1	50,867,201	4,197	23,241	664	17,169	Tree	Venezuela	Kim et al., 2020	NCBI	
	<i>F. decemcellulare</i>	-	NRRL 13412	ASM1326620v1	53,686,487	3,482	35,228	467	18,126	<i>Coffea</i> sp.	Dominican Republic	Kim et al., 2020	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium fujikaroi</i>	<i>F. fujikaroi</i>	FFUJI	IMI 58289	IMI58289_V2	43,832,314	12	4,234,805	5	14,810	Rice	China	Wiemann et al., 2013	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium sambucinum</i>	<i>F. graminearum</i>	FGRAM	PH-1; NRRL 31084	ASM24013v3	36,458,046	19	8,914,601	2	13,313	Wheat kernels	USA Michigan	Cuomo et al., 2007	NCBI	
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>lycopercisi</i>	FOXYL	4287	ASM14995v2	61,386,934	85	4,589,937	6	27,347	Tomato	Spain Murcia	Ma et al., 2010	NCBI	
	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	-	Fo47; NRRL 54002	ASM1308505v1	50,358,849	12	4,523,040	5	17,127	Endophyte	NA	Wang et al., 2020	NCBI	
NA	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	-	ARSEF 2860	ASM28067v1	33,697,794	237	84,720	114	10,364	NA	NA	Xiao et al., 2012	NCBI	

Table 5: All *Fusarium* genomes used in the phylogenomic analysis and comparative studies.

Core, fast-core and lineage-specific chromosomes assignment.

Scaffold sequences shorter than 450 kb were not included in this assignment. Lineage-specific chromosomes (LSCs) were assigned based on: (1) reduced number or no synteny regions linked by single-copy orthologous genes between chromosomes of FSSC species, (2) higher repeat proportion and (3) lower GC content compared to the core chromosomes. Note that not all LSCs fulfilled all three characteristics mentioned above. The designated LSCs include chromosome 13, 14 of Fu3, chromosome 13, 14, 15 of Fu6 and Ph1, chromosome 13, 14, 15 and 16 of LHS11, chromosome 13 to 19 of LHS14 and chromosome 7, 14 to 23 of Fs6. Chromosomal syntenic regions were determined by linking 9,101 single-copy orthologous genes shared among the FSSC genomes. For this analysis, OGs were determined via OrthoFinder (v2.3.8; Emms & Kelly, 2019) using 11 *Fusarium* genomes (six genome assemblies created from this study, *F. vanettenii* 77-13-4, *F. solani* FSSC5, *F. oxysporum* 4287, *F. graminearum* Ph-1, and *F. fujikuroi* IMI58289). Visualization of the synteny was plotted using R package 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016) in R (v.3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020) using *F. falciforme* Fu3 genome as reference. Fast-core chromosomes were determined by comparing proportion of FSSC-unique gene across all FSSC chromosomes. FSSC-unique gene is referred as orthologous genes not found in *F. fujikuroi* IMI58289, *F. graminearum* PH-1, and *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopercisi* 4287 genomes (Wiemann et al., 2013; Cuomo et al., 2007; Ma et al., 2010). To check for "uniqueness" of each chromosome, proportion of single-copy orthogroup shared amongst the genomes in comparisons were determined. The comparisons included (1) amongst the six FSSC genomes and (2) FSSC genomes to three other non-FSSC genomes mentioned above. The higher the shared genome number indicates higher level of commonness of the chromosome. Any chromosome contained more than 50 % of common genes ('6' in comparison 1 and '3' in comparison 2) were core chromosomes.

3.3 Results

Genome characteristics of six sequenced FSSC isolates.

We sequenced the genomes of five species within the clade 3 of FSSC. These species included one *F. falciforme* (Fu3), two *F. keratoplasticum* (Fu6 and LHS11), and one *Fusarium* sp. FSSC12 (LHS14), which were isolated from various aquatic animal hosts. Two species of plant host origins - *Fusarium* sp. (Ph1) and *F. vanettenii* (Fs6) were also chosen for comparative purposes. Initial assembly was produced from averaging 121X of Oxford Nanopore reads (sequence N50 = 14 - 23 kb) using the Flye assembler (Kolmogorov et al., 2019) and were further polished by Illumina reads (**Table 3**). The final assemblies were in 14 to 65 pieces with of N50 3.2 to 4.2 Mb (**Table 4**) averaging 56 Mb which is more contiguated and comparatively larger than other representative *Fusarium* genomes (ranging 33 - 61 averaging 46 Mb; **Table 5**). Interestingly, *F. vanettenii* Fs6 has an assembly of 77.4 Mb, which is the largest *Fusarium* genome reported to date and larger than the published *F. vanettenii* MPVI 77-13-4 genome of 51.2 Mb (Coleman et al., 2009), suggesting high intraspecies variation. The assemblies were The *F. falciforme* Fu3 reference was amongst the most complete genome, which consists of 14 contigs with six telomere-to-telomere gapless chromosomes (**Table 6**) and were in average 17 times more contiguated than the published FSSC genomes (N90: 2.7 vs. 0.0004 - 2.6 Mb, respectively; last accessed date 18th January 2021).

Genome assembly	Total number of contigs	CCCTAA on both ends	CCCTAA on single end
Fu3	14	Fu3.chr03	Fu3.chr02
		Fu3.chr04	Fu3.chr05
		Fu3.chr08	Fu3.chr09
		Fu3.chr11	
		Fu3.chr13	
		Fu3.chr14	
Fu6	25	NA	NA
LHS11	23	LHS11.chr03	LHS11.chr01
		LHS11.chr08	LHS11.chr02
		LHS11.chr09	LHS11.chr04.1
		LHS11.chr10	LHS11.chr06.1
		LHS11.chr11	LHS11.chr06.2
		LHS11.chr12	LHS11.chr07.1
		LHS11.chr13	LHS11.chr07.2
		LHS11.chr14	LHS11.scaf16
			LHS11.scaf17
			LHS11.scaf18
			LHS11.scaf19
	LHS11.scaf22		
LHS14	34	NA	NA
Ph1	17	Ph1.chr04	Ph1.chr01.1
		Ph1.chr07	Ph1.chr01.2
		Ph1.chr08	Ph1.chr02.1
		Ph1.chr09	Ph1.chr02.3
		Ph1.chr10	Ph1.chr03.1
		Ph1.chr11	Ph1.chr03.2
		Ph1.chr13	Ph1.chr05
		Ph1.chr14	Ph1.chr06.1
			Ph1.chr06.2
			Ph1.chr12.1
			Ph1.chr12.3
			Ph1.chr15
			Ph1.scaf17
Fs6	60	Fs6.chr01	Fs6.chr03
		Fs6.chr07	Fs6.chr06.1
		Fs6.chr08	Fs6.chr06.2
		Fs6.chr10	Fs6.chr09
		Fs6.chr11	Fs6.chr12.1
		Fs6.chr14	Fs6.chr12.2
		Fs6.chr17	Fs6.scaf16
		Fs6.chr20	Fs6.scaf18
			Fs6.scaf21
			Fs6.scaf22
			Fs6.scaf23
			Fs6.scaf24
			Fs6.scaf26
			Fs6.scaf35
			Fs6.scaf52
	Fs6.scaf58		

Table 6: Scaffold assembly status determined using TRF and manually written python script identifying hexamer sequence 'CCCTAA' on each sequences of the genome assemblies. Chromosome is defined as sequence containing telomere on both sequence ends.

We predicted 14,927 to 19,146 protein encoding genes from these assemblies using MAKER2 (Holt & Yandell, 2011) pipeline with proteomes from closely related fungi and transcriptome reads generated from mycelium. Analysis of Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs (BUSCO; Manni et al., 2021) indicated that the proteomes were 98.3 to 100 % complete (**Table 4**). Overall, 73.6 – 77.1 % of these genes were assigned protein family or domain (Pfam) via eggNOG-mapper (Cantalapiedra et al., 2021), further signifying the completeness of these assemblies. Orthology of the six sequenced assemblies, 17 other *Fusarium* genomes and an outgroup species *Beauveria bassiana* (**Table 5**) was inferred using OrthoFinder (Emms & Kelly, 2019). A total of 24,203 orthogroups (OGs) were inferred in which 16,154 (66.7 %) and 235 (1.0 %) OGs were *Fusarium* and FSSC-specific, respectively. All six genomes contained predicted average of 420 (2.6 % of total gene) and 487 genes encoded for effector and carbohydrate active enzyme, respectively (**Table 6**). Besides, an average number of 46 secondary metabolite biosynthetic gene clusters were detected in the six genomes, which roughly half of the predicted metabolites are associated with plant pathogenicity. These metabolites include squalestatin S1, declauxin, fusarin, sansalvamide, demethylcoprogen, and oxyjavanicin (**Table 8**; Ma et al., 2013). All these additional gene annotations revealed similar number of gene features typically comparable to other *Fusarium* genomes.

The repeat content of most FSSC genomes ranged from 4.2 to 9.4, averaging 7.1 %, with the exception of *F. vanettenii* Fs6 which contained 17.7 % (**Figure 13a**). This unusually large repetitive DNA content is most possibly contributing to its large genome size, along with expansion of gene number (**Table 4**). Upon looking into the repeat content, DNA transposons constituted the largest proportion (averaging 48.4 %) of FSSC genomes (**Figure 13b**) followed by LTR retrotransposons averaging 26.5 %.

Species delimitation within FSSC has been challenging due to almost indistinguishable isolate morphology and high similarity in nucleotide identity (refs). We conducted multilocus sequence typing (MLST) analyses comparing the

Assembly	Total number of protein coding gene	Number of predicted gene with signal peptide	Number of predicted effector gene	% out of total gene	Apoplastic	Cytoplasmic
<i>F. falciforme</i> Fu3	15,124	1,454	427	2.8	270	157
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i> Fu6	14,927	1,431	403	2.7	257	146
<i>F. keratoplasticum</i> LHS11	15,044	1,440	405	2.7	258	147
FSSC12 LHS14	15,929	1,499	416	2.6	263	153
<i>Fusarium sp.</i> Ph1	15,493	1,466	409	2.6	255	154
<i>F. vanettenii</i> Fs6	19,146	1,665	460	2.4	291	169

Table 7: Number of signalP predicted effector genes in each assembly.

BGC	<i>F. falciforme</i> Fu3	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i> Fu6	<i>F. keratoplasticum</i> LHS11	FSSC12 LHS14	<i>Fusarium sp.</i> Ph1	<i>F. vanettenii</i> Fs6
T1PKS	15	14	15	14	14	19
T3PKS	1	1	2	2	1	2
NRPS	12	11	11	11	11	13
NRPS-like	6	7	7	8	8	7
terpene	6	7	6	7	9	10
phosphonate	1	1	1	1	1	1
indole	1	2	2	1	2	2
RiPP-like	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	42	43	44	44	46	55

Table 8: Number of secondary metabolites biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) detected via antiSMASH.

Most similar known product							
	BGC	Fu3	Fu6	LHS11	LHS14	Ph1	Fs6
squalestatin S1	terpene	v	v	v	v	v	v
gibepyrone-A	terpene	v	v	v	v		v
declauxin	T1PKS	v	v*	v	v	v	v
NG-391/fusarin	T1PKS; NRPS	v*	v	v	vw	v	v
sansalvamide	NRPS	v	v	v	v	v	v
demethylcoprogen	NRPS	v*	v	v	v	v	v
cyclosporin C	NRPS; T1PKS	v	v	v		v	
oxyjavanicin	T1PKS	v	v	v	v	v	v
clavaric acid	terpene		v	v	v	v	v
aspteric acid	terpene		v			v	v
pyranonigrin E	NRPS-like				v		
fusaric acid	NRPS-like; T1PKS				v		
curvupallide-B	T1PKS; NRPS				v		
monacolins K	T1PKS					v	
gibberellin	terpene					vw	
koraiol	terpene						vw

Table 9: Secondary metabolites biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) detected via antiSMASH. Single 'v' represents one gene copy.

Figure 13. Proportion of (a) genome features and (b) repeat content in the six sequenced FSSC assemblies. SINE was found in Fu3, LHS14 and Fs6 for 0.12, 0.05 and 0.05 % respectively and were not noticeable in the plot.

sequence identity and constructed a maximum likelihood phylogeny based on 40 FSSC species (**Figure 14; Figure 15; Table 1**). Even though most of the species were resolved based on the phylogeny, the pairwise comparison of sequence identity in some FSSC species was higher than 98 % even in different species, consistent with the limitation of using just a few molecular markers. We further determined the genome average nucleotide identity (ANI) and detected a lower average of 94.5 % among the FSSC species comparisons. For instance, *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 had a nucleotide similarity of 98.6 % in MLST sequence but 94.7 % in genome, demonstrating a better distinction to resolve FSSC species at genome level. Ph1 was most closely related to *F. solani* haplotype FSSC5 (MLST and genome ANI: 98.2 and 94.7 %). Based on MLST analysis, strain LHS14 was designated as haplotype FSSC12 and the first genome assembly of this species (**Figure 15**). Finally, we constructed a species phylogeny using 2,385 single-copy orthologs which recapitulated the relationship based on MLST and ANI and determined that species were not grouped by animal or plant hosts (**Figure 14b; Figure 16; Table 5**).

Evolutionary dynamics of FSSC chromosomes.

To investigate whether lineage-specific chromosomes (LSCs) were present in each *Fusarium* species, we assessed the extent of chromosome linkage between species via pairwise single copy orthologs, proportions of repetitive elements and FSSC-unique genes in each chromosome. In addition to assigning the core and LS chromosomes as in previous *Fusarium* studies (Coleman et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2010), FSSC chromosomes were also categorised into two compartments as well as revealing a spectrum of conservation (**Figure 17a**). The majority of chromosomes were part of linkage group that were shared by all six species and designated as core chromosomes (CCs). On the other end of conservation spectrum were LSCs which contained single copy orthologs shared by mostly two out of six genomes and lower proportion of common genes. This compartmentalisation of conservation spectrum was more apparent upon further examination of FSSC chromosome linkage with three other non-FSSC *Fusarium* species, revealing three compartments within the

Figure 14. Sequence similarities and phylogenomic of *Fusarium*. (a) Pairwise comparisons of species identity determined by multilocus sequences (ITS+TEF+RPB2) routinely used for *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC) in the lower green-shaded triangular matrix and genome average nucleotide identity in selected *Fusarium* species in upper orange-shaded triangular matrix. Darker shading indicates higher sequence similarity. (b) A subset of *Fusarium* phylogenomic tree from **Supplementary Figure 5**. The tree was constructed using 2,385 single-copy orthogroup sequences. Species name in bold represents strains sequenced in current study and source origin (host) represented by icons.

Figure 15. Multi-locus sequence typing phylogenetic tree of ITS, RPB2, and TEF1 regions in *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC). Asterisk indicates > 80 % bootstraps value. Species name in bold indicates isolate sequenced in current study.

Figure 16. Genome phylogeny of 23 *Fusarium* assemblies and *Beauveria bassiana* as the outgroup constructed using 2,385 single-copy orthogroup sequences. Asterisk indicates 100 % bootstrap value. Coalescent unit on scale bar applies on internal branch only. Orange box indicates the FSSC clade. Species name in bold represents genomes sequenced in this study. Source origin (host) of isolates represented by icons.

Figure 17. *Fusarium* chromosome features. (a) Proportion of one-to-one gene shared across each chromosome among the FSSC genomes. Asterisk (*) in black and white indicates gapless chromosome and chromosome contained higher proportion of FSSC-unique genes, respectively. (b) Proportion of one-to-one gene shared across each chromosome among FSSC genomes with three *Fusarium* genomes outside of FSSC, including _ for comparison. The proportion of (c) repeat and (d) FSSC-unique gene of each chromosome of the six FSSC genomes. Statistical significance was calculated using unpaired-Wilcoxon test (*: $P < 0.001$; ns = $P > 0.05$). CC = Core chromosome; LSC = Lineage-specific chromosome; FCC = Fast-core chromosome.

Fusarium genomes by harbouring lower proportion of common gene than CCs (**Figure 17b**). This additional compartment was made up by chromosome 7, 11, and 12 (CC 8, 12 and 13 of Fs6) of FSSC genomes, in which all chromosome 7 harbouring the least proportion of common genes amongst the CCs. Hence, this suggested a common evolutionary process acting on the respective chromosome of all FSSC species.

Synteny analysis revealed that CCs were highly syntenic between the FSSC species than LSCs and harbour significantly less repeat (mean 7.0 vs. 31.3 %, respectively; **Figure 17c; Figure 18 and 19a**), which are hallmarks of *Fusarium* genome evolution (Bertazzoni et al., 2018). We designated 12 core and 2 to 11 LSCs, respectively in each FSSC genome. The CCs constitute the majority (67.7 – 94.7 %) of genomes, while the gapless LS chromosomes averaging 1.2 Mb, which is similar markup with *F. oxysporum* genomes (Ma et al., 2010). However, large variations in telomere-to-telomere LSC length were observed in FSSC ranging from 0.8 Mb in chromosome 13 of *Fusarium* sp. Ph1 to 3.3 Mb in chromosome 14 of *F. vanettenii* Fs6.

We observed consistent proportions of FSSC-unique genes across corresponding chromosomes of each FSSC genome, with CC 7, 11 and 12 (CC 8, 12 and 13 of Fs6) contained significantly higher proportion of FSSC-unique genes compared to other CCs, but were similar when compared to LSCs (**Figure 17d; Figure 19b**). CC 7, 11 and 12 are hereafter referred as fast-core chromosomes (FCCs). The combined mean size of FC chromosome was approximately 2.8 Mb, with FSSC-unique genes ranging from 26.8 to 35.4 % of the total gene content (vs. 7.7 – 22.1 % in other CCs). Lower number of FSSC-specific genes were detected in LSCs compared to the other CCs (averaging 59 vs. 272 genes) but the former constitutes at least one-fifth of the total gene content. In terms of gene locality, sub-telomeric bias was detected for these FSSC-unique genes, a similar trend which were previously reported in *F. graminearum* (Cuomo et al., 2007) and *Aspergillus* genomes (Fedorova et al., 2008). This phenomenon was consistent across all six FSSC genomes, except for FCCs in which these genes were distributed across whole chromosomes (**Figure 20**).

Figure 18. Synteny analyses of FSSC genomes with *F. falciforme* Fu3 as reference show (a) number of single-copy orthogroup shared between chromosomes and (b) chromosomal location of these single-copy genes. col of AC

Figure 19. Proportion of repetitive elements and FSSC-unique genes of each chromosome. Chromosome 7 of Fs6 is corresponding to accessory chromosome 13 of other genomes.

Figure 20. Location of FSSC-unique genes across genomes. Single red line indicates one gene.

We compared *F. falciforme* Fu3 with *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopercisi* strain 4287 (Fol4287; Ma et al., 2010), a genome of species beyond FSSC and carrying LSCs. Based on synteny analysis, macrosynteny was not observed in Fu3 chromosome 7, 11, and 12 – the FCCs (**Figure 21**). All these evidences suggest FCCs harbour distinctive features compared to the other CCs and LSCs.

All chromosome 7 (chromosome 8 of Fs6) of FSSC genomes were located at the end of CCs in the conservation spectrum (**Figure 17a and b**), suggesting this chromosome is more “accessory” compared to other CCs. First, repeat proportion of chromosome 7 was the highest among all CCs (**Figure 17c; Figure 19a**). Second, frequent rearrangements were observed in chromosome 7 across FSSC genomes (**Figure 18**). Although the rearrangement pattern varied in each genome, most of it were seen translocated to FCCs and LSCs of each genome, represented by number of single-copy orthogroup of chromosome 7 (**Figure 18a**). Interestingly, intraspecies chromosomal structural variations were observed between *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 and LHS11 in which translocations of *F. falciforme* Fu3 chromosome 7 were observed in chromosome 3, 13 and 14 of *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 but was dissimilar in LHS11 (**Figure 18b**). Hence, shorter scaffold length in chromosome 7 of Fu6 suggests loss of accessory regions and translocated to other chromosomes in the genome. In summary, higher proportion of repeat content, frequent and varied rearrangement suggest chromosome 7 represents a more unique or “accessory” behaviour compared to other CCs.

Evolutionary scenario of FSSC chromosome evolution.

Examining the characteristics that differentiate between CCs, FCCs and LSCs in the six genomes had allowed us to discover unique features which were consistent across chromosome type. FCCs contained higher repeat and FSSC-unique gene proportions compared to CCs, suggesting a dissimilar evolutionary pressure on both of these chromosome types and FCCs may evolve at a different speed and as an evolutionary hotspot for niche adaptation- and pathogenicity-related genes. Nonetheless, structural characteristics varied when compared among the LSCs,

Figure 21. Dotplot comparison showing synteny between genomes of *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopercisi* 4287. Red dotted line represents unique chromosomes of Fu3. Blue dotted box represents mesosynteny between the two genomes.

suggesting independent evolutionary state in each of the LSCs. We hereby propose an evolutionary process of FCC formation (**Figure 22**) in addition to the “two-speed genome” concept in genome of fungal pathogens (refs). One of the potential processes involving formation of new accessory chromosome is duplication of CC, followed by repeat induced point mutation (Bertazzoni et al., 2018). Other than accumulations of repeat elements, FSSC-unique genes may also accumulate on certain CCs during niche expansion. These CCs, possibly turned into FCCs, may signify the additional genome compartment that underwent independent evolutionary process as revealed by the conservation spectrum across the chromosomes (**Figure 17a and b**). In addition, higher repeat proportion in chromosome 7 compared to the other CCs may allow rapid rearrangement of this chromosome, potentially benefiting niche expansion. Besides, FCCs may also undergo repeat induced mutation which is then turn into accessory chromosome.

3.4 Discussion

The FSSC genomes show high conservation of synteny among the core chromosomes (CCs), but diverse number, sizes, and rearrangements in lineage-specific chromosomes (LSCs). Besides LSCs, the fast-core chromosome (FCC) 7, 11 and 12, which contained higher proportion of FSSC-unique genes compared to other chromosomes, may represents another crucial evolutionary hotspot for niche adaptation specifically for FSSC species. Diversity of LSCs in these assemblies supported the evidence of broad range niches in FSSC species, which can be recognized from its isolation sources, as well as in other *Fusarium* species with certain specific niche (O’ Donnell et al., 2016). For instance, FSSC 12 is so far restricted to only associated to infection of marine animal hosts. LSCs of FSSC are not mainly enriched in effector, carbohydrates active enzyme and secondary metabolite-related genes, as the proportions is similar to the CCs. This is contrasting with other pathogenic filamentous fungi such as *F. poae* and _ (Witte et al., 2021, refs).

Figure 22. Schematic diagram showing hypothetical process of core-unique and accessory chromosome formation.

Chapter 4: Transcriptomic analysis of *Fusarium solani* species complex during infection

4.1 Introduction

The most prevalent *Fusarium* pathogens associated with veterinary infection were species from the phylogenetically and species-rich clade 3 of *Fusarium solani* species complex (FSSC; Zhang et al. 2006; O'Donnell et al., 2008; O'Donnell et al., 2016; Schroers et al., 2016), which are ubiquitously present in the environment (Zhang et al., 2006). Several FSSC species were reported to cause disease in marine animals such as grey seal, shrimp, dolphin, and whale (O'Donnell et al., 2016). For instance, two species from the FSSC clade 3 – *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum*, were the predominant species occurring in diseased sea turtle nests worldwide (Sarmiento-Ramírez et al. 2014). Koch postulates was validated using *F. keratoplasticum*, confirmed its ability to cause disease and high mortality rate (83.3 %) on sea turtle *Caretta caretta* eggs (Sarmiento-Ramírez et al., 2010). The disease is now termed sea turtle egg fusariosis (STEF; Smyth et al., 2019) and had caused low hatching success of eggs (Phillott and Parmenter, 2001) from both natural nests (Phillott et al., 2004; Sarmiento-Ramírez et al. 2014) and man-made hatcheries (Nordahlawate et al., 2017; Hoh et al., 2020). However, the pathology associated with STEF is less known.

Studies regarding the virulence of FSSC on pea (*Pisum sativum*) had determined pea-specific pathogenic genes – the *PEP* cluster, which is located on accessory chromosome (AC; Han et al., 2001; Temporini & VanEtten, 2002). Experimental removal of AC and gene *PDA1* (pisatin-demethylating ability), which is located within the *PEP* cluster, had shown reduced virulence on pea. This experiment also shows that AC was dispensable for its survival (Wasmann & VanEtten, 1996). Besides the *PEP* cluster, other genes involved in establishing disease in plant were also describe from some of the members within FSSC. For example, the gene *cut1* and *NhABC1*, which are located on the core chromosomes (CCs) of *F. solani*, are also involved in pea virulence (Rogers et al., 1994; Coleman et al., 2011). This explained

the presence but weak virulence of pea even after removal of AC (Wasmann & VanEtten, 1996; Coleman *et al.*, 2016). In addition, since pea-*F. solani* is one of the model systems in studying host-pathogen interaction, disease resistance mechanism of pea against *F. solani* pathogenesis was characterized (Hadwiger, 2008; Hadwiger, 2015).

Although pathogenic mechanism of *F. solani* on plants had been substantially described, it is unknown whether this mechanism is similar on FSSC that infects animals. This one-sided focuses of *F. solani*'s pathogenicity and infection mechanism on plants should encourage similar investigations to be made on animal hosts since they are equally critical. This part of the study aims to compare and describe the basic pathology of FSSC isolates infecting animals, in terms of (1) morphological characteristics, (2) disease establishment, and (3) molecular infective mechanism. Terrapin eggs will be used during the experiment to imitate disease situation as in sea turtle eggs. Transcriptomes of FSSC which is developing disease on the eggs at different time points will be sequenced and analysed. The expressed genes during the infection will be used to compare and validate the results from comparative genomic analysis of Chapter 2 to confirm the prediction of pathogenic-related genes. Results of Chapter 2 and 3 should provide a clearer understanding of FSSC infective mechanism on animals and may aid in future development of management strategies which limit the damage caused by this pathogen.

4.2 Methodology

Attraction assays.

To determine if pathogen *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 will be attracted by the egg host, an attraction assay experiment was set-up as following: glass tubes were horizontally filled with one-third volume of 1.5 % water agar. An approximately 0.5 cm³ agar block from 1.5 % water agar fungal culture cultivated for five days was carefully inserted into the end of the glass tube without touching the tube surface and bottom agar. At the opening of the glass tube, the egg was fixed

using cling film and rubber band while a stopper was used in the control treatment (Figure 23a). Speeds of hyphae growth were recorded every day for

Figure 23. Host attraction assay. (a) Experimental setup for control treatment using stopper (left) and experimental treatment using *Pelodiscus sinensis* egg (right). (b) Hyphae growth rate of all treatments had no significant differences after each group comparisons with Wilcoxon-test.

nine days. The experiment was repeated twice with a total of 38 samples (tubes) assessed. Statistical tests for the comparison between the treatments was performed using Wilcoxon test via package 'ggpubr' (function: stat_compare_means; v.0.4.0; Kassambara, 2020) in R (v.3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020).

Histology during initial disease establishment.

F. falciforme Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 cultures in ½ PDA at 28 °C cultivated for seven days were prepared for the following experiments. Eggs were inoculated by placing an approximately 1 cm² fungal agar block on the shell surface and incubated at 28 °C. After five days, the agar block was removed and eggshell fragments surrounding the agar block were cut and collected for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and laser scanning confocal microscopy (LSM) observations. For SEM, eggshell fragments were first fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde and 2.5 % glutaraldehyde in 1x PBS buffer for 1 hour at 4 °C. Samples were then washed with 1x PBS buffer thrice for 10 minutes each, followed by second fixation using 1 % osmium tetroxide-buffered solution for 1 hour in the dark at room temperature. Fixed samples were washed again as previously described and went through a serial dehydration step using EtOH at 30, 50, 70, 80, 90, 95, and 100 % concentration for 10 minutes at each step. Dehydration using 100 % EtOH was repeated twice and samples were then dried in Pelco CPD#2400 CO₂ critical point dryer (Ted Pella Inc., Redding, CA, USA). Finally, samples were coated with a layer of gold with Sputter Coater 108 auto (Cressington Scientific Instruments, Watford, UK) and examined using Quanta 200 ESEM (FEI Company, Hillsboro, OR, USA). For LSM, eggshells fragments were placed into warm 1.5 % agarose and waited until solidified. Each sample embedded in agarose was transferred to a 50 mL Falcon tube and fixed with 10 % formalin overnight at room temperature. Fixed samples were washed with PBS buffer thrice, and then kept in PBS buffer for storage in 4 °C until further processing. Sample embedding and undecalcified sectioning procedures followed Wada et al. (2016). Each section was cut into 8 µm thickness on Leica CM3050 cryostat (Leica Microsystems, Nussloch, Germany). The sections were stained with Calcofluor White Stain (Sigma-Aldrich, Product #18909) for few minutes, excess stain washed

with water, and mounted with ProLong™ Gold Antifade Mountant (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, #P36930), followed by removing excess mountant solution and covered with coverslip. Slides were kept at 4 °C in the dark until LSM observation. Samples were examined using LSM 880 (ZEISS, Germany) and visualized with Zen2.3 software (black edition, ZEISS, Germany). Signals of Calcofluor White were excited with 405 nm laser and detected in range 410 – 523 nm. DIC (differential interference contrast) images were also acquired. All image acquisitions were scanned with a 40x objective lens in z-stack mode (0.391 μm). The z-stack images were prepared with a maximum intensity projection through Zen2.3 software (Lite edition, ZEISS, Germany).

Animal sample preparation.

Animal experiments were evaluated and approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) of Academia Sinica, Taiwan under protocol ID 18-05-1214. Freshly laid and fertilized soft-shelled turtle (*Pelodiscus sinensis*) eggs were purchased from a local farm in Pingtung, Taiwan and sent to the laboratory. The eggs were embedded in styrene foam to avoid movement-induced mortality during transportation. Top of the egg surface were marked with pencil to ensure eggs were not rotated during the following process: egg surface was cleaned with a brush to remove dirt and sterilized by immersing eggs into 75 % EtOH for one minute, 1 % bleach + Tween 20 solution for one minute, and autoclaved distilled water for one minute. Egg surface was wiped dry using clean tissue and half-buried in sterilized and moist vermiculite (1 g water/1 g vermiculite) in a plastic container covered with cling film. Each container contained ten eggs and were incubated in a climate chamber (Panasonic, MLR-352H) at 28 °C and 60 % relative humidity in the dark until the 30th day. On day 30, the eggs were observed using the candling technique to check for embryo viability. These embryos were estimated to be developed to stage TK21 to 22 as described in Tokita and Kuratani (2001). Dead eggs were removed and alive eggs were kept for following experiments which included pathogen inoculation, host attraction assay and eggshell observations. Any alive

embryos remaining after all experiments were humanely euthanized following the standardized procedures approved by IACUC.

Animal inoculation with FSSC.

During candling observation, the location of the embryo and directly opposite to the embryo (upper pole) were marked. The observed and alive eggs were half-buried on fresh sterilized and moist vermiculite with embryos placed at the lower pole (buried). A tiny hole was carefully made on top of the eggshell and this created a small air space under the hole and above the egg content. Two fungal pathogen species - *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6, which were previously isolated from dead sea turtle eggs, were used to perform the inoculation experiment. The cultures were incubated on ½ PDA at 28 °C for seven days and spore suspension was prepared by washing the mycelium with 1x PBS solution and filtered to keep only spores. Haemocytometer-estimated 10^7 spores/mL suspension was injected into the egg's air space through the tiny hole without poking the egg content. The inoculated eggs were left incubated for another three to four days. The mycelium of Fu3 and Fu6 under the same culture condition were collected at the 4th day as the positive control of this experiment. After three to four days-post-infection, eggs were made broken to check and record the embryo's vitality. Samples collected for RNA isolation are of two types depending on the egg's condition during collection: the presence of obvious white substances (blotches or cotton-wool-like growth) on the egg content and/or fungal-growth on the opaque eggshell membrane (**Figure 24**). Since this experiment focused on the pathogen, we tried to collect only the white substances and the shell membrane with obvious fungal growth. Each sample type was considered one sample. Samples were collected using sterilized forceps and kept immediately in Trizol reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #15596026) and - 80 °C until further processing.

Total RNA isolation, library preparation and sequencing.

RNA isolation was carried out according to the TRIzol reagent protocol. At the cell lysis step, each sample in 2 mL screw-cap tube was mixed with six to eight

0.8 mm stainless steel beads, flash-freezing the tubes in liquid nitrogen, and homogenized using PowerLyzer24 homogenizer (MoBio Laboratories, Carlsbad, CA, USA, Cat. #13155) set to 3000 x g for 20 sec and repeated at least twice to ensure the sample was homogenized. Isolated RNA was quantified using Invitrogen Qubit® 4

Figure 24. Chinese soft-shelled turtle *P. sinensis* egg inoculated with spores of *F. falciforme* Fu3 or *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6. (a) Fu6, four-days post inoculation. (b) Fu3, three-days post inoculation. (c) Fu6, three-days post inoculation. Arrowhead indicates fungal colonization on egg membrane as mycelium mass (a) or on the egg content as white blotches (b, c). Scale bar is approximately 5 mm.

Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and checked for integrity in 1.5 % agarose gel. Samples with adequate concentration and show no degradation were chosen for RNA sequencing. In total, 20 samples were sequenced, which include three Fu3 and three Fu6 positive controls (mycelium from PDA media), seven Fu3 and seven Fu6 infected samples. Paired-end library were prepared for the RNA samples using NED Next® Ultra™ RNA Library Prep Kit and sequenced on Illumina NovaSeq 6000 instrument with 150 bp paired-end reads.

RNA-seq read processing, mapping, and cross-mapping check.

Raw RNA reads were trimmed to remove adaptor sequences and poor-quality reads using fastp (-l 30; v0.20.1; Chen et al., 2018). Trimmed reads of each sample were mapped to their respective genome (Fu3 or Fu6) according to the inoculation treatment and the host *P. sinensis* genome (GCF_000230535.1_PelSin_1.0; Wang et al., 2013) using STAR (v2.7.7a; Dobin et al., 2013). Mapping rate of samples' RNA reads on genomes shows that most of the reads (74.9 - 86.1 % of infected samples) were mapped to the host genome (**Supplementary Table X**). To obtain additional mapped read count of pathogens for further analyses, we selected and re-sequenced four infected samples with the highest mapping rate on pathogen genomes (two from Fu3 and Fu6 treatment, respectively). The re-sequenced samples were FM1, FB3, KM1 and KM2. The additional sequenced reads were combined with their respective samples of the first sequencing batch and at least 5 Mb of mapped reads per sample were obtained. The four samples in total comprised of 14,301,244 and 13,556,180 mapped Fu3 and Fu6 reads, respectively. Combined reads were re-processed from the beginning from trimming to genome mapping. To ensure RNA reads which mapped on the *Fusarium* genomes are not from the host, we performed cross-mapping checks on both fungal and host mapping files. First, read IDs were cross-checked to identify reads that are mapped to both genomes. The CIGAR score of these read IDs were then compared. Lastly, CIGAR score of mapped reads which were lower on Fu3 or Fu6 genomes compared to *P. sinensis* genome were removed from further analyses. These processed reads were then parsed to featureCounts (-p -s 2; v2.0.1; Liao et al., 2014) to create a count matrix.

No.	Sample ID	Raw reads	Raw data (G)	Filtered reads	Filtered %	Read pairs	Mapping rate to genome						Read cross check with host		
							Host - <i>Pelodiscus sinensis</i>		Pathogen - Fu3		Pathogen - Fu6		Paired read removed	%	Remaining paired reads
							Mapped pairs	%	Mapped pairs	%	Mapped pairs	%			
1	FC1	39,713,156	6	39,511,944	99.5	19,755,972	-	-	19,591,330	99.2	-	-	-	-	-
2	FC2	41,720,728	6.3	41,533,722	99.6	20,766,861	-	-	20,599,330	99.2	-	-	-	-	-
3	FC3	42,108,156	6.3	41,855,556	99.4	20,927,778	-	-	20,715,277	99.0	-	-	-	-	-
4	FB1	47,667,996	7.2	47,073,886	98.8	23,536,943	19,535,830	83.0	53,418	0.2	-	-	399	0.7	39,689
5	FB2	46,718,656	7	46,124,294	98.7	23,062,147	19,248,263	83.5	28,472	0.1	-	-	363	1.3	20,808
6	FB3	206,768,436	30.4	204,349,118	98.8	102,174,559	80,019,133	78.3	6,687,834	6.5	-	-	2,991	0.0	6,325,562
7	FB4	49,433,014	7.4	48,757,968	98.6	24,378,984	20,041,957	82.2	54,462	0.2	-	-	323	0.6	47,608
8	FM1	149,273,720	21.9	147,347,170	98.7	73,673,585	55,302,403	75.1	7,613,410	10.3	-	-	2,736	0.0	5,425,779
9	FM2	33,212,592	5	32,887,642	99.0	16,443,821	14,166,124	86.1	177,883	1.1	-	-	229	0.1	140,767
10	FM3	51,359,100	7.7	50,814,666	98.9	25,407,333	20,922,326	82.3	165,083	0.6	-	-	308	0.2	154,545
11	KC1	49,124,212	7.4	48,950,078	99.6	24,475,039	-	-	-	-	24,281,485	99.2	-	-	-
12	KC2	44,871,734	6.7	44,685,776	99.6	22,342,888	-	-	-	-	22,147,145	99.1	-	-	-
13	KC3	38,760,750	5.8	38,611,946	99.6	19,305,973	-	-	-	-	19,129,541	99.1	-	-	-
14	KB1	44,687,386	6.7	44,209,394	98.9	22,104,697	18,743,463	84.8	-	-	36,558	0.2	394	1.1	30,851
15	KB2	43,386,546	6.5	42,872,370	98.8	21,436,185	17,576,604	82.0	-	-	403,392	1.9	542	0.1	392,487
16	KB3	47,500,704	7.1	46,951,280	98.8	23,475,640	19,751,476	84.1	-	-	15,003	0.1	646	4.3	5,414
17	KB4	42,495,198	6.4	42,014,214	98.9	21,007,107	17,586,870	83.7	-	-	121,823	0.6	1,818	1.5	62,024
18	KM1	528,075,418	77.7	522,916,144	99.0	261,458,072	213,028,518	81.5	-	-	6,979,091	2.7	6,336	0.1	6,736,070
19	KM2	177,413,814	26.1	175,553,510	99.0	87,776,755	65,846,035	75.0	-	-	6,577,089	7.5	7,112	0.1	5,921,932
20	KM3	43,194,328	6.5	42,699,632	98.9	21,349,816	17,854,260	83.6	-	-	20,561	0.1	800	3.9	1,630

Table 10: RNA-seq and read statistics of FSSC-animal infection experiment. Samples FB3, FM1, KM1, KM2 were sequenced twice to increase number of pathogen reads for further analyses.

Differential gene expression analyses and functional enrichment.

We identified differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in Fu3 and Fu6 between infected and control samples using DESeq2 (padj < 0.05; v1.24; Love2014) in R (v3.6.3; R Core Team, 2020). Functional enrichment of the DEGs were identified using R package 'topGO' (v 2.36.0; Alexa & Rahnenführer, 2019). We used the same pipeline as described for analysis of host's RNA reads to determine the DEGs of the infected host. For comparison, RNA-seq dataset of *P. sinensis* embryos from different embryo developmental stages (TK19 and TK23) generated by Wang et al. (2013) were chosen as the control because our samples were collected between TK21 to 22. A total of 24,408 *P. sinensis* genes were produced for differential expression analysis. Of those, 12,419 genes were differentially expressed (adjusted P value < 0.05), with 5,815 up- and 6,604 down-regulated genes during the infection experiment.

4.3 Results

Fusarium falciforme and *F. keratoplasticum* are opportunistic pathogens of animal host.

We analysed the infection scenarios of *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 inoculated on eggs of animal host Chinese softshell turtle (*Pelodiscus sinensis*). Extensive hyphae growth of both species was observed on top of eggshell surface after five days of inoculation (**Figure 25**) with some occasionally growing into the cavity-like structure (**Figure 26**). Cryo-sectioning and histological observations of undecalcified eggshell cross-sections revealed presence of both *Fusarium* species on the outer, within the calcareous, and inner layers of the eggshells (**Figure 25**), confirming the hyphae penetration through eggshell. Degradations were sometimes observed on the eggshell membrane (**Figure 25**). Attraction assays revealed no significant difference in hyphae growth speed towards eggshell in either *Fusarium* species ($P = 0.67$ in *F. falciforme* and $P = 0.86$ in *F. keratoplasticum*, Wilcoxon-test; **Figure 23**) or between species ($P = 0.86$ in control and $P = 0.86$ in inoculated, Wilcoxon-test). We further examined the symptoms of *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* colonization on eggs three- and four- days post inoculation (**Figure 24**). Mycelium mass can be observed growing on the membrane (**Figure 24a**) and

Figure 25. Laser confocal microscopy images show fungal stained with Calcofluor White (blue signal) in undecalcified cross-section of *Pelodiscus sinensis* eggshell. 'os' indicates outer surface of eggshell and 'im' indicates the inner eggshell membrane. Scale bar is 50 μm.

F. falciforme Fu3

F. keratoplasticum Fu6

Figure 26. Scanning electron microscopy images of Chinese soft-shelled turtle *P. sinensis* eggshell inoculated with *F. falciforme* Fu3 or *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 show fungal hyphae spreading on the eggshell surface, arrowhead indicates hyphae growing into cavity-like structure.

embryo (**Figure 24b and c**). Some inoculated eggs exhibited reduced branching point and disrupted blood capillaries despite embryo still alive during the examination (**Figure 24c**). Together, these observations confirmed that these two FSSC species are opportunistic animal pathogens where upon contact, fungal hyphae can penetrate into eggshell via natural openings and subsequently lyse and colonise egg content.

Gene expression pattern of FSSC and animal host during infection experiment.

To better understand how FSSC able to infect aquatic animals, we inoculated *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 on *Pelodiscus sinensis* eggs, generated and compared transcriptome-wide gene expression data of both species. Principal component analysis (PCA) shows that expression pattern of single copy orthologs among *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 pathogens were separated by treatment types (**Figure 27a**; all sequenced samples in **Figure 26**), indicating both pathogen species responded distinctly after contacting an animal host compared to culture media. Significant high correlation was found in expression of single copy orthologs in inoculated samples (**Figure 28**; Log_2 TPM, $R^2 = 0.78$, $P < 2.2e^{-16}$) and slightly higher compared to the control samples (**Figure 29**; Log_2 TPM, $R^2 = 0.66$, $P < 2.2e^{-16}$), suggesting both species adopted similar colonization and infection strategy while contacting animal host. In addition, expression in host inoculated with either *Fusarium* were highly correlated (Log_2 TPM, $R^2 = 0.98$) suggesting the turtle host also responded almost equally to either pathogen.

Differentially expressed genes of FSSC during infection experiment.

A total of 4,185 and 4,111 genes were differentially expressed (adjusted P value < 0.05) in the infection experiment of treatment *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6, respectively. Fu3 treatment comprised of 1,823 up- and 2,362 down-regulated genes whereas Fu6 treatment comprised of 2,241 up- and 1,870 down-regulated genes (**Figure 27b**).

Since two pathogen species of the FSSC were used in the experiment, we seek to understand a general overview of common genes regulated by FSSC pathogens

Figure 27. Differentially expressed (DE) genes of *Fusarium falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplaticum* Fu6 inoculation on animal host *Pelodiscus sinensis* shown in (a) principal component analysis (PCA) and (b) number of regulated orthogroup and gene among the two pathogens. Number in bracket represents number of genes. (c)

Figure 28. Principal component analyses of pathogens' gene expression pattern of all sequenced samples in (a) *F. falciforme* Fu3 (sample name starts with F) and (b) *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 (K) infecting animal host.

Figure 29. Correlation plots of log₂ normalized transcript per million (TPM) of one-to-one orthologous gene of Fu3 and Fu6 in control (mycelium) samples.

during animal infection. We explored the differentially up-regulated co-expressed genes among the two pathogens and determined a total of 523 orthologous genes. This includes 535 and 555 genes from Fu3 and Fu6 treatment, respectively (**Figure 25**). Based on gene ontology (GO) analysis of these co-expressed genes, both pathogens interacted with host by displaying positive regulations of immune system processes and defense responses. Both pathogens also exhibited responses towards stimuli, pH, osmotic stress, nutrient levels, metal ions and inorganic substances (**Table 10**). For uniquely expressed genes in each pathogen species, a total of 1288 and 1867 genes were up- and down-regulated in Fu3 treatment, respectively. In Fu6, the up- and down-regulated unique genes were 1686 and 1397, respectively. Upon comparison of these unique upregulated genes, it is surprisingly found that several genes encoded for CFEM domain were of different orthogroups. We further detected additional two genes encode for CFEM domain in Fu6 treatment (**Table 11**).

In Fu3 treatment, the most differential expressed genes include members in processes such as carbohydrates transport and metabolism, energy production and conversion, and intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport based on annotation of Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs) category. Of particular interest, the most differential expressed gene as well as six other members within top 100 were annotated to contain CFEM (Common in Fungal Extracellular Membrane) domain, a cysteine-rich and fungal-specific protein domain which was proposed to involve in fungal pathogenicity (ref). In addition, some genes also encode for diverse transporter proteins which targeted sugars, irons, and amino acids. The functions of some of the highest expressed genes were different comparing between Fu3 and Fu6 treatment. In Fu6 treatment, the top 100 genes of highest \log_2 FC generally involved in processes that include transport and metabolism of carbohydrates and inorganic ions. Most of these proteins were sugar transporters from the Major Facilitator Superfamily (MFS). In contrary to Fu3, only single gene out of the top 100 contained CFEM domain, and this gene was in different orthologous group with the up-regulated CFEM domain genes of Fu3.

ID	log2FoldChang	medianTPM_C	medianTPM_U	Orthogroup	gff_chr_loc	eggnog_COG_category_x	eggnog_Prefer	eggnog_Descr	eggnog_Pfam	antisemash	signalP	Effector	phibase_gene	phibase_tax	phibase_desc	strdb_preferred	strdb_stringdb
Fu3_00167100	-3.893867061	15.32752786	307.0346166	OG0000003	Fu3.chr01	C - Energy production & conversion	ALD5	Belongs to the Aldolase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_03239	Aldehyde dehy
Fu3_00174700	-1.896157296	349.3126588	970.036586	OG0001639	Fu3.chr01	C - Energy production & conversion	OSM2	to soluble form Cys-H5-FAD_h	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_08791	Hypothetical pr
Fu3_01303200	-5.9793754	0.91483206	29.6378575	OG0000133	Fu3.chr11	C - Energy production & conversion	DL1D	D-lactate dehyd/FAD-oxidase_N	NA	NA	NA	GZZC021	Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	NA	NA	FW93_1488	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00067800	-1.691160028	91.17972215	228.5938476	OG0000213	Fu3.chr01	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	CYS3	Cystathionine c Cys_Met_Met_u	NA	NA	NA	NA	insetB_PXO_Xanthomonas_reduced_virule	FOQG_07473	Cystathionine g		
Fu3_00187400	-5.314053426	6.181620905	172.0567093	OG0006459	Fu3.chr01	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	-	Belongs to the L-Asparaginase	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_14733	L-asparaginase
Fu3_00212100	-3.322452024	0.773713296	6.867629492	OG0000623	Fu3.chr02	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	-	Amino acid perAA_peramide_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00288800	-3.738136791	21.2259177	21.89643221	OG0000623	Fu3.chr02	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	-	Amino acid perAA_peramide_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00296400	-2.305992453	50.6241967	206.9675699	OG0002356	Fu3.chr02	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	BAT2	Belongs to the Aminotran_4	NA	NA	NA	NA	Fghat12_(FGS)Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	FOQG_04485	Branching-chain		
Fu3_00372900	-2.728513764	3.660392413	20.70574418	OG0001151	Fu3.chr03	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	CHA1	Pyridoxal-phos PALP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00353700	-3.063416208	16.39329292	151.4562601	OG0001394	Fu3.chr04	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	TCRP	4-hydroxyphen Glyoxalase.Gly	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_02318	4-hydroxyphen
Fu3_00641100	-1.566860017	48.79772385	120.7139715	OG0000900	Fu3.chr05	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	CAR1	Belongs to the Arginase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_05477	Arginase; Beta
Fu3_01170800	-1.669768995	43.47884805	142.437027	OG0004112	Fu3.chr09	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	SER1	Aminotransfer Aminotran_5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_8601	Related to 3-ph
Fu3_01207900	-3.666499316	7.381199365	90.0415159	OG0004631	Fu3.chr10	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	BNAS	Catalyses the c1Aminotran_5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_10891	Kynureninase
Fu3_00987700	-7.03452212	0	1.20367274	OG0000354	Fu3.chr08	EH - Amino acid transport and metabolism: Coenzyme transport and metabolis	ILV2	acetoalate syn TPP_enzyme cNA	NA	NA	NA	Molv2	Magnaporthe_c_loss_of_pathog	FOQG_07020	Acetoadactate sy		
Fu3_00708400	-2.843611693	12.67761944	80.91447104	OG0000884	Fu3.chr05	ET - Amino acid transport and metabolism: Signal transduction mechanisms	FAA4	fructose-bisphc/FP_alkolase_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FGI0119.1	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00668800	-2.413954061	49.75423258	218.9188228	OG0000525	Fu3.chr05	F - Nucleotide transport and metabolism	ADE12	Plays an impor Aderylsucc_sy	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	CCT64198	Probable ADE1
Fu3_01154400	-1.854106115	2.264292888	8.646027939	OG0004985	Fu3.chr09	F - Nucleotide transport and metabolism	-	Belongs to the NUP	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_7914	Related to puri
Fu3_00404900	-3.533192705	2.597351387	24.6243612	OG0009673	Fu3.chr03	G - Carbohydrates transport and metabolism	CHT2	Glycosyl hydr/ CBM_19FCelb	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00473700	-3.143809511	1.578446603	25.19968183	OG0001517	Fu3.chr03	G - Carbohydrates transport and metabolism	manf	Belongs to the CBM_1.CelbII	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00790900	-1.319743001	382.5024519	764.7264487	OG0003465	Fu3.chr06	G - Carbohydrates transport and metabolism	FBA1	fructose-bisphc/FP_alkolase_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG02770.1	Uncharacterize
Fu3_01240900	-2.56800068	21.73057337	106.339909	OG0004269	Fu3.chr10	G - Carbohydrates transport and metabolism	PLB1	Cytoplasmic pPLA2_B	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_5759	Probable lysol
Fu3_00649300	-2.153089746	3.23493452	12.15224317	OG0000120	Fu3.chr05	I - Lipid transport and metabolism	FAA4	AMP-binding cAMP-binding_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_1052	Related to long-
Fu3_00550000	-7.170592855	0.985994576	15.8190324	OG0000213	Fu3.chr08	I - Lipid transport and metabolism	-	to long-chain-fcAMP-binding	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG433.1	Hypothetical pr
Fu3_00295900	-2.821059363	74.66047197	474.500598	OG0000296	Fu3.chr04	K - Transcription	RM101	AMP-binding cAMP-binding_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	pH-response tr
Fu3_00029000	-2.613847203	18.32359664	109.2359636	OG0002738	Fu3.chr01	O - Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones	MNN4	LiCd family LiCd	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_04835	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00142100	-1.673601666	59.73227769	145.3887097	OG0009704	Fu3.chr01	O - Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones	TRR1	Belongs to the Pvr_redox_2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_2739	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00105900	-2.644697618	270.4213844	1610.383455	OG0007166	Fu3.chr03	O - Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones	AHP1	Redoxin Redoxin	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_819	Probable pero
Fu3_00628200	-4.305366426	4.021248225	84.5530208	OG0009241	Fu3.chr06	O - Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones	alp	Homologues of the Dyr_redox_1	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00445400	-4.445419411	2.96328665	195.551315	OG0000628	Fu3.chr10	OP - Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones	alp	Belongs to the Cation_A_TPPas	NA	SP	NA	NA	FGSG_03315	Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	LW93_048	Related to endo	
Fu3_00027500	-8.91273518	1.771713984	776.6310669	OG0001561	Fu3.chr01	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	PHO89	Sodium-phosph PHO4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_04862	Phosphat tras
Fu3_00224500	-4.186313805	3.653769365	77.8354286	OG0008133	Fu3.chr02	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	HXT5	Belongs to the Sugar_tr	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG05042.1	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00463800	-3.141637905	7.74956929	99.2162847	OG0007748	Fu3.chr03	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	FFS1	Belongs to the MIP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG0248.1	Hypothetical pr
Fu3_00593100	-1.322912308	22.49436536	49.1414707	OG0009496	Fu3.chr04	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	PHO13	4-nitrophen lpHydrolase_6H	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_11712	4-nitrophenyl
Fu3_01003600	-2.773338872	81.11737887	557.4517046	OG0000050	Fu3.chr08	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	ENA2	Belongs to the Cation_A_TPPas	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_04138	Potassium/sodi
Fu3_01285300	-3.94707382	2.544849644	381.1382108	OG0000288	Fu3.chr10	P - Inorganic ion transport and metabolism	FTR1	to high-affinity_FTR1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	ftre1	Related to high
Fu3_00311300	-5.151059648	10.20294884	431.430217	OG0005185	Fu3.chr02	Q - Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism	Q - Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism	L-lysine 6-mom X_oxycnase	NA	NA	NA	NA	SID1	Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	LW93_13873	Related to L-on	
Fu3_00655300	-3.627466904	1456.218271	21053.33604	OG0000314	Fu3.chr05	Q - Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism	ADH1	alcohol dehydr/ADH_NADH	NA	NA	NA	NA	MoADH1	Magnaporthe_c_unaffected_pat	FOQG_05325	Alcohol dehyd	
Fu3_01417200	-8.75769081	0.018697996	18.24862929	OG0004744	Fu3.chr12	Q - Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism	-	nonribosomal p_AMP-binding	NA	NA	NA	NA	NP56	Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	LW93_030	Related to AM-	
Fu3_00519200	-4.910778224	76.39651477	204.3891923	OG0004946	Fu3.chr06	S - Function unknown	PRA1	Putative peptid/HRXHX	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_07600	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00097200	-7.281789965	1.771281009	282.0707697	OG0009862	Fu3.chr01	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Siderophore inMFS_1_1TR12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_08590	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00226700	-7.313397071	0.440103887	53.8167504	OG0006543	Fu3.chr02	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Fungal siderophore inMFS_1_1TR12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_10671	Related to majo
Fu3_00405300	-3.33478767	8.063242894	70.0778351	OG0010349	Fu3.chr03	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	to MSF drug trMFS_1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_1088	Related to multi
Fu3_00428200	-10.70770922	0	15.38406471	OG0009179	Fu3.chr03	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Major Facilitator MFS_1_1TR12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_1271	Related to majo
Fu3_00469800	-8.22237411	0	2.8304302	OG0013365	Fu3.chr03	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Major Facilitator MFS_1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00473200	-8.98921856	0.241478465	73.23117268	OG0011622	Fu3.chr03	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Major Facilitator MFS_1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00769800	-8.572940298	0.199390674	59.5359359	OG0012672	Fu3.chr06	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Siderophore inMFS_1_1TR12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00813400	-11.13355895	0.191869176	258.2233761	OG0012293	Fu3.chr06	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	-	Fungal siderophore inMFS_1_1TR12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_01186500	-3.855907304	6.026152211	79.7159137	OG0001844	Fu3.chr09	U - Intracellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport	SIF1	Major Facilitator MFS_1_3Agg	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_8223	Probable SIF1
Fu3_00129600	-3.7064295	449.8459774	4515.861437	OG0000003	Fu3.chr01	C - Energy production & conversion	ALD5	Belongs to the Aldolase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_03239	Aldehyde dehy
Fu3_00630100	-11.35645689	0	54.27534882	OG0000003	Fu3.chr06	C - Energy production & conversion	ALD5	Belongs to the Aldolase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOG0979.1	Uncharacterize
Fu3_00892900	-1.02708811	227.4126793	397.4083861	OG0006291	Fu3.chr06	C - Energy production & conversion	IUS1	Scaffold proteinNu_U	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOG2624.1	Iron-sulfur clus
Fu3_01286100	-5.92311227	0.54510449	28.0057059	OG0000133	Fu3.chr11	C - Energy production & conversion	DL1D	D-lactate dehyd/FAD-oxidase_N	NA	NA	NA	GZZC021	Fusarium_gran_unaffected_pat	LW93_1488	Uncharacterize		
Fu3_00185600	-4.462242991	42.93376601	388.0582399	OG0006459	Fu3.chr01	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	-	Belongs to the L-Asparaginase	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_14733	L-asparaginase
Fu3_00207200	-6.992312155	0.189823007	16.2427532	OG0000623	Fu3.chr02	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	-	Amino acid perAA_peramide_N	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00378500	-4.79352027	3.90694109	84.75331334	OG0001151	Fu3.chr04	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	CHA1	Pyridoxal-phos PALP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00573900	-4.130667569	17.86028998	236.6672098	OG0001394	Fu3.chr05	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	TCRP	4-hydroxyphen Glyoxalase.Gly	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_02318	4-hydroxyphen
Fu3_00681300	-1.934063966	91.68049744	298.6408949	OG0009001	Fu3.chr05	E - Amino acid transport and metabolism	CAR1	Belongs to the Arginase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_05477	Arginase; Beta
Fu3_00983900	-6.437008814	0	4.301573988	OG0000354	Fu3.chr08	EH - Amino acid transport and metabolism: Coenzyme transport and metabolis	ILV2	acetoalate syn TPP_enzyme cNA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Molv2	Magnaporthe_c_loss_of_pathog	FOQG_07020	Acetoadactate sy	
Fu3_01105800	-3.949453354	1.630725442	18.8710101	OG000498													

ID	log2FoldCha	medianTPM	medianTPM	gff_chr_loc	eggnog_COG	eggnog_Prefe	eggnog_Description.x	eggnog_PFAMs	antismash	signalP	Effector	phibase_gene	phibase_tax	phibase_desc	strdb_prefer	strdb_stringc
Fu3_00751500	-13.590337	0.18697375	1514.00495	Fu3.chr05	S	-	CFEM domain	CFEM	NA	SP	NA	FGSG_01588	Fusarium_gra	unaffected_pi	NA	NA
Fu3_01358300	-12.342149	0.7887955	3169.5618	Fu3.chr11	S	-	CFEM domain	CFEM	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_01282200	-12.291109	0.35719042	2770.89345	Fu3.chr10	S	-	CFEM domain	CFEM	NA	SP	Apoplasic	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu3_00937900	-10.90412	1.44455868	2397.7861	Fu3.chr07	S	-	protein ubiquitination	-	NA	SP	Apoplasic/cy	NA	NA	NA	LW93_14360	Uncharacteriz
Fu3_01283200	-8.0031506	10.7264798	2689.51145	Fu3.chr10	T	-	Four repeated domains in th	Fasciclin	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_5674	Related to TG
Fu3_00540300	-3.8379761	492.606336	5805.74921	Fu3.chr04	P	-	Belongs to the ATPase C ch	ATP-synt_C	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG06048.1	Uncharacteriz
Fu3_00655300	-3.6274669	1456.21827	21055.336	Fu3.chr05	Q	ADH1	alcohol dehydrogenase	ADH_N,ADH_zin	NA	NA	NA	MoADH1	Magnaporthe	unaffected_pi	FOQG_05325	Alcohol dehy
Fu3_01016200	-3.6030983	405.395694	6134.58559	Fu3.chr08	S	-	CVNH	CVNH	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_5281	Related to cya
Fu3_00025300	-3.5639882	256.20095	4173.72425	Fu3.chr01	S	-	GPR1 FUN34 YaaH-class pla	Grp1_Fun34_Ya	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG01580.1	GPR1/FUN34,
Fu3_00550800	-2.8061044	87.2145955	592.699072	Fu3.chr04	C	PYC1	Catalyzes a 2-step reaction,	Biotin_carb_C,Bi	NA	NA	NA	GzC2H048	Fusarium_gra	unaffected_pi	LW93_7474	Pyruvate carb
Fu3_01187200	-2.165488	341.720625	1481.88656	Fu3.chr09	E	mpdA	mannitol-1-phosphate dehy	Mannito1_dh,Mai	NA	NA	NA	Mpd1	Parastagonos	unaffected_pi	FOQG_02103	Hypothetical j
Fu3_00652900	-1.8727065	848.493265	2953.49972	Fu3.chr05	C	CYC1	Electron carrier protein. The	Cytochrom_C	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_05355	Cytochrome c
Fu3_00658500	-1.4144085	237.876438	765.35717	Fu3.chr05	E	MET6	Cobalamin-independent syr	Meth_synt_1,Me	NA	NA	NA	MSY1	Fusarium_gra	reduced_viru	FOQG_05282	5-methyltetra
Fu3_00598600	-1.281292	691.955684	1439.88231	Fu3.chr04	S	-	Stm1	HABP4_PAI-RBP	NA	NA	NA	PemG1	Magnaporthe	effector_(plar	LW93_1750	Related to RA
Fu6_01103700	-14.770132	0.30431612	6535.10098	Fu6.chr09	E	-	GMC oxidoreductase	GMC_oxred_C,C	NA	NA	NA	AOX1	Passalora_ful	reduced_viru	FOQG_00057	Alcohol oxida
Fu6_01345700	-13.178182	0	1309.33427	Fu6.chr11	S	-	GPR1/FUN34/yaaH family	Grp1_Fun34_Ya	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_3152	GPR1 protein;
Fu6_01104200	-11.187298	2.41403417	7491.57266	Fu6.chr09	Q	-	L-lysine 6-monooxygenase	FMO-like,Pyr_re	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_12477	Hypothetical j
Fu6_01273800	-10.91197	3.65409359	5253.75908	Fu6.chr10	T	-	Four repeated domains in th	Fasciclin	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_5674	Related to TG
Fu6_01438500	-8.5806292	4.58348729	1405.74796	Fu6.chr12	-	-	-	-	NA	SP	Apoplasic/cy	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01272900	-7.9530095	17.238168	4306.96567	Fu6.chr10	S	-	CFEM domain	CFEM	NA	SP	Apoplasic	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00809700	-7.3253111	6.47002157	1095.91303	Fu6.chr06	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	SP	Apoplasic/cy	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01104100	-7.1316769	1.24812448	4031.47362	Fu6.chr09	V	-	Beta-lactamase	Beta-lactamase	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG02875.1	Hypothetical j
Fu6_01435300	-7.0735099	0.12359617	18.6255496	Fu6.chr12	-	-	-	-	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00210500	-7.0566176	13.6763464	1565.73516	Fu6.chr02	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00344500	-5.5147425	31.6476201	1437.10597	Fu6.chr03	P	-	Belongs to the major facilita	Sugar_tr	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_10071	Hypothetical j
Fu6_01013500	-5.4359707	54.7510092	2213.18337	Fu6.chr08	S	-	to ethanolamine utilization f	Cupin_3,EutQ	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG05681.1	Hypothetical j
Fu6_00880500	-4.6935291	32.9911342	711.196882	Fu6.chr06	S	-	Protein of unknown functio	DUF4449	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_12912	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_00073200	-4.3941551	188.072175	3482.76885	Fu6.chr01	-	-	-	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01009600	-4.1925263	503.073271	9239.38447	Fu6.chr08	S	-	CVNH	CVNH	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_5281	Related to cya
Fu6_00044200	-4.1769736	275.728329	4901.6587	Fu6.chr01	S	-	4-coumarate coenzyme A li	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG01379.1	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_01362300	-4.1761761	76.7244045	1199.51883	Fu6.chr12	S	-	Bulb-type mannose-specific	B_lectin	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01383700	-3.9303462	166.654311	2443.22988	Fu6.chr12	S	-	Nitrogen starvation-induce	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00129000	-3.7062915	449.545797	4515.86144	Fu6.chr01	C	ALD5	Belongs to the aldehyde deh	Aldedh	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_03239	Aldehyde deh
Fu6_00097100	-3.6728731	632.088091	7091.15283	Fu6.chr01	S	-	Extracellular matrix protein	GPI-anchored	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01271400	-3.5780693	194.755414	1977.39182	Fu6.chr10	O	TTR1	Glutaredoxin	Glutaredoxin	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_09150	Glutaredoxin
Fu6_00808100	-3.5767841	377.976291	4107.62998	Fu6.chr06	S	-	Putative peptidase family	HRXXH	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_07600	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_00168000	-3.5438555	264.863473	3027.26747	Fu6.chr01	P	-	ZIP Zinc transporter	Zip	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG09303.1	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_01347500	-3.4007129	197.391026	1976.6957	Fu6.chr11	S	-	CFEM domain	CFEM	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00695200	-3.3719965	809.467075	7388.74998	Fu6.chr05	Q	ADH1	alcohol dehydrogenase	ADH_N,ADH_zin	NA	NA	NA	MoADH1	Magnaporthe	unaffected_pi	FG10855.1	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_00056900	-3.0337065	841.270372	4707.65807	Fu6.chr01	S	-	Shwachman-Bodian-Diamor	SBD5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FG01267.1	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_01347700	-2.6540706	192.813875	1094.86761	Fu6.chr11	Q	katG	Belongs to the peroxidase f	peroxidase	NA	NA	NA	FvCP01	Fusarium_ver	unaffected_pi	FOQG_12684	Catalase-perc
Fu6_00864800	-2.5766183	379.454066	2055.58474	Fu6.chr06	O	-	Thioredoxin	Thioredoxin	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_12794	Probable thio
Fu6_00755800	-2.4751837	2573.49795	10054.8708	Fu6.chr05	S	PMP3	Proteolipid membrane poter	Pmp3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00309200	-2.4696816	557.055779	2573.25149	Fu6.chr02	-	-	-	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_01147700	-2.3435067	486.6725	2371.33369	Fu6.chr09	C	FDH1	Catalyzes the NAD()-depen	2-Hacid_dh,2-H	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	FOQG_02458	Formate dehy
Fu6_00681500	-2.2134574	356.8034	1580.65957	Fu6.chr05	-	-	-	-	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fu6_00410700	-1.578675	2326.78731	6241.49267	Fu6.chr03	O	AHP1	Redoxin	Redoxin	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_819	Probable perc
Fu6_00809300	-1.4231173	863.399399	1932.95436	Fu6.chr06	S	-	Cerato-platanin	Cerato-platanin	NA	SP	NA	NA	NA	NA	LW93_461	Uncharacteriz
Fu6_00785700	-0.7286571	492.206043	700.529891	Fu6.chr05	O	PRB1	Belongs to the peptidase S8	Inhibitor_I9,Pept	NA	SP	NA	PRB1	Fusarium_gra	reduced_viru	FG00192.1	Uncharacteriz

Table 12: Functional annotation of unique upregulated gene expression in Fu6 treatment

Upon inspections of all up-regulated genes during animal infection, a total of 77 and 92 effector genes were identified from Fu3 and Fu6 treatment, respectively. Some of these effectors were known to involve in plant pathogenicity. For instance, necrosis-inducing proteins (NPP1), pectate lyases (PELA and PELB), Cerato-platanin (CP), GAS1, and trichothecene (MoCDIP-like) effector genes were up-regulated in both animal infection treatments. Some of the up-regulated CFEM domain genes were also annotated as effectors. Besides, 63 and 77 secondary metabolite gene clusters were also detected from Fu3 and Fu6 treatment, respectively. Some of these genes encode for cytochrome P450 (or pisatin demethylase; PDA) and ABC transporters, which were commonly reported in FSSC during pea infection. In Fu3 treatment, several secondary metabolism genes required for synthesis of the mycotoxin Fusarin C were also found to be up-regulated during the experiment. Several genes encoding carbohydrate active enzymes which degrade plant materials such as pectin, cellulases and chitinases were also determined.

Co-expression of genes of FSSC-animal infection were not associated with core-unique and lineage-specific chromosomes

Based on previous *Fusarium*-infection studies, several pathogenicity-related genes can be found on the accessory or LSCs (Rep & Kistler, 2010; Coleman, 2016; Yang et al., 2020) and we speculated that a larger proportion of genes may be differentially expressed in these chromosomes compared to the CCs. We performed chi-square tests between DEG number in CCs, FCCs and LSCs of *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 respectively and observed no such pattern (Fu3: $\chi_1^2 = 10.7$, $P = 0.005$; Fu6: $\chi_1^2 = 205.81$, $P < 2.2e^{-16}$). In addition, no genes were differentially expressed in *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 LSC 13, 14 and 15 (**Figure 30**). This indicates FSSC genes in FCCs and LSCs are not necessarily required for animal pathogenesis.

Pathogen inoculation triggered the host's defence.

We analysed DEGs of infected host and compared it to RNA-seq dataset of *P. sinensis* embryos of various developmental stages generated by Wang et al. (2013) study. A large difference can be seen between the gene expression pattern of host

Figure 30. The distribution of all differentially expressed genes of FSSC-animal infection experiment in (a) *F. falciforme* Fu3 and (b) *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6. Each red line represents single gene.

inoculated by FSSC and the natural developing host embryo on similar egg incubation days (PC1: 95 % variance; **Figure 31**), signifying host responded distinctly to FSSC infection. Excluding genes which are related to embryo development, other upregulated genes with enriched GO term of infected host show numerous genes which are related to biological processes involving host immunity, response, and defence to another organism (**Table 13**). Specifically, positive regulations of immune response towards stress and external biotic stimulus were detected. These regulations include leukocytes activation, cytokines production, apoptotic process, and defence response (**Figure 32**).

4.4 Discussion

Understanding the genetic diversity within FSSC's capability of infecting cross-kingdoms is of fundamental evolutionary interest and essential for management of emerging wildlife diseases. Here, we successfully established the first *Fusarium*-aquatic animal infection model which utilised high-throughput sequencing technology on Chinese softshell turtle (*Pelodiscus sinensis*), produced highly contiguated assemblies for five FSSC species, and examined their gene expression patterns of *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* during colonization on an animal host.

We also visually observed initial disease development of these pathogens on turtle eggs. One of the purposes of selecting *P. sinensis* egg as the model organism for this study is to understand the disease conditions during FSSC-sea turtle egg infection. Sand for sea turtle eggs incubation may contain high FSSC abundance and this will increase the risk of eggs being infected (Hoh et al., 2020). We questioned if FSSC in the sand is attracted by the incubating eggs in the nest and attraction assays indicated no signs of host-attraction. This suggested chance-encounter of FSSC pathogens on eggs, unlike some fungal pathogens that seek hosts actively in the environment (ref). During plant infection, hyphae of fungal pathogens penetrate into host tissue through natural openings such as stomata or lenticels (ref). While

eggshell serves as a protection for the developing embryos, we observed both *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* are capable of invading egg content through the

Figure 31. Principal component analyses of gene expression patterns compared between *P. sinensis* host inoculated by *F. falciforme* (sample name starts with F) or *F. keratoplasticum* (K) and natural developing host (DRR).

GO.ID	GO.Term	Annotated	Significant	Expected	classicFisher
GO:0002376	immune system process	1298	743	477.62	1.00E-30
GO:0050776	regulation of immune response	433	276	159.33	1.00E-30
GO:0080134	regulation of response to stress	825	461	303.57	2.50E-30
GO:0048584	positive regulation of response to stimulus	1337	673	491.97	4.00E-26
GO:0050778	positive regulation of immune response	334	210	122.9	1.50E-22
GO:0002684	positive regulation of immune system process	519	329	190.97	1.00E-30
GO:0002682	regulation of immune system process	775	462	285.17	1.00E-30
GO:0006955	immune response	711	430	261.62	1.00E-30
GO:0002252	immune effector process	435	271	160.07	7.80E-28
GO:0045321	leukocyte activation	445	274	163.74	5.80E-27
GO:0002520	immune system development	614	357	225.93	6.20E-28
GO:0046649	lymphocyte activation	375	225	137.99	2.60E-20
GO:0071345	cellular response to cytokine stimulus	420	262	154.55	4.50E-27
GO:0034097	response to cytokine	492	302	181.04	2.80E-29
GO:0001816	cytokine production	415	264	152.71	3.20E-29
GO:0001817	regulation of cytokine production	372	240	136.88	5.60E-28
GO:0006915	apoptotic process	1052	573	387.1	1.00E-30
GO:0097190	apoptotic signaling pathway	352	217	129.52	1.10E-21
GO:0012501	programmed cell death	1118	617	411.39	1.00E-30
GO:0008219	cell death	1261	684	464	1.00E-30
GO:0042981	regulation of apoptotic process	899	485	330.8	4.10E-27
GO:0043067	regulation of programmed cell death	942	509	346.62	1.20E-28
GO:0010941	regulation of cell death	1083	580	398.51	1.00E-30
GO:0071216	cellular response to biotic stimulus	141	105	51.88	7.00E-20
GO:0006950	response to stress	2122	1132	780.82	1.00E-30
GO:0009607	response to biotic stimulus	691	412	254.26	1.00E-30
GO:0009605	response to external stimulus	1763	822	648.72	2.40E-19
GO:0006950	response to stress	2122	1132	780.82	1.00E-30
GO:0033554	cellular response to stress	1032	592	379.74	1.00E-30
GO:0006952	defense response	827	473	304.31	1.00E-30
GO:0051716	cellular response to stimulus	3408	1615	1254.03	1.00E-30
GO:0031347	regulation of defense response	385	230	141.67	2.10E-20
GO:0080135	regulation of cellular response to stress	417	245	153.44	2.70E-20
GO:0044403	biological process involved in symbiotic interaction	234	170	86.1	3.40E-29
GO:0098542	defense response to other organism	366	239	134.68	5.00E-29
GO:0051707	response to other organism	669	396	246.17	1.00E-30
GO:0043207	response to external biotic stimulus	669	396	246.17	1.00E-30
GO:0044419	interspecies interaction between organisms	255	183	93.83	3.20E-30

Table 13: Gene ontology (GO) terms of genes which were differentially expressed in infected host.

Figure 32: Schematic diagram summarizing processes of FSSC-egg infection.

eggshell and cause tissue degradation of egg membrane. Previous study had also shown calcium depletion of eggshell post-infection by FSSC (Phillott _), suggesting lytic activity of pathogen. Nevertheless, the eggshell of *P. sinensis* is thicker than sea turtle eggshell with expanded calcareous layer (ref), signifying the feasibility of egg penetration process. A drawback of the inoculation experiment was failing to capture a time-series process during the colonization. We failed to assess embryo's viability due to difficulties such as egg candling after pathogen inoculation. Hence, during the time which collection of RNA samples was the only one-time measurement of viability. Nevertheless, the experiment provided a more general overview of the disease mechanism and colonization process while we focused on the similarities among *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 pathogens.

Plant pathogenicity-related genes can be determined in all six FSSC genomes based on the available annotations mostly from comparatively well-studied *Fusarium*-plant host infection system, and some of them were found significantly regulated in the animal infection experiment. Few previous studies were carried out to understand *Fusarium* pathogenicity on animal hosts targeting genes of known virulence factors based on knowledge from the fungal-plants infection systems. FSSC strains tested on mice resulted in 100 % mortality rate compared to other tested strains from species such as *F. oxysporum* and *F. verticillioides* (Mayayo et al., 1999). *F. falciforme* of environmental origin and clinical *F. keratoplasticum* strains also significantly reduced the survival rate in *Drosophila melanogaster* fly, confirming FSSC is highly virulent towards animals regardless of its isolation source. In *F. oxysporum*-animal infection models, studies intended to compare the differences of infective mechanisms between plant and animal hosts. We found several common genes encoded for biological processes shared by both pathogens *F. falciforme* Fu3 and *F. keratoplasticum* Fu6 during the animal infection experiment. Most of the FSSC up-regulated genes can be linked to transports, suggesting vigorous transports of wide varieties of materials or compounds towards and out of animal cells during the infection. Several genes known to involve in plant pathogenesis, particularly some carbohydrate active enzymes which functions to degrade plant cell wall materials.

Nevertheless, the role of CFEM domain in animal infection remained to be elucidated. Study of genes in LSCs were usually relevant in *Fusarium* pathogens (refs), however, the pattern was not obvious in animal infection, at least up to the extent of this experiment. In summary, only few differences were found between gene expression of *F. falciforme* and *F. keratoplasticum* even though they isolated from same host and underwent same inoculation experiment, suggested these two species take similar approaches or adopting universal virulence mechanisms in causing disease in animals. These results suggested FSSC species are opportunistic pathogen on animals. Pathogen of different strains or not closely related to one another phylogenetically may infect the same host, and its pathogenicity traits might be similar in the conserved region such as effectors (Summerell et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2016).

4.5 Conclusion

To conclude, our combined results have revealed several features associated to animal infection on these pathogens. Our results provided new insights into the genomic characteristics of animal-infecting FSSC species and its disease development and colonization particularly on turtle eggs.

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Data availability

All sequences generated from this study were deposited on NCBI following BioProject number as below:

Chapter 2:

BioProject PRJNA560331 – Isolate MLST sequences and amplicon raw reads.

Chapter 3:

BioProject PRJNA782245 – Isolate MLST sequences, raw DNA sequences and genome assemblies.

Chapter 4:

BioProject PRJNA782245 – Raw RNA sequences.